

Application of Machine Learning Algorithms and Mathematical Modelling to Optimise University Learning Analytics

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MSc in Computing (Research)**

By

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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	2
DEDICATION	4
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	5
LIST OF FIGURES	6
LIST OF TABLES	7
GLOSSARY	8
STUDENT DECLARATION	10
RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS	11
ABSTRACT.....	12
Chapter 1 INTRODUCTION.....	13
1.1 Introduction.....	13
1.2 Aim and Objectives.....	14
1.3 Central Research Questions:	15
1.4 Limitations of Study	16
1.5 Thesis Structure	17
Chapter 2 LITERATURE REVIEW	19
2.1 Learning Analytics, Student Engagement and Success	19
2.2 Artificial Intelligence, Blended Learning and Learning Analytics	22
2.3 Learning Analytics and Machine Learning.....	23
2.4 Student Feedback and Learning Analytics.....	26
2.5 Data Protection in Learning Analytics.....	27
2.6 Gaps Identified.....	29
2.7 Literature Review Summary.....	30
Chapter 3 METHODOLOGY OVERVIEW	31
3.1 Introduction.....	31
3.2 Methodology Framework.....	31
3.3 Learning Environment	33
3.4 Data Protection Steps.....	36
Chapter 4 DATA INSIGHTS AND PATTERNS.....	37
4.1 Introduction.....	37
4.2 Datasets Used for this Research.....	37
4.3 Datasets Description	38
4.4 Data Extraction Process	41

4.5 Data Processing.....	43
4.6 Data Visualisation Overview	45
4.7 Descriptive Statistics.....	46
4.9 Exploratory Data Visualisation and Insights.....	47
4.9.1 Visualisations and Insights using Boxplots.....	48
4.9.2 Histogram: Visualisation and Insights	53
4.9.3 Scatter and Correlation Plots: Visualisation and Insights.....	56
4.10 Chapter Summary	59
Chapter 5 MACHINE LEARNING ANALYSIS AND RESULTS	61
5.1 Introduction.....	61
5.2 Analytics	61
5.3 Statistical Basis for Feature Selection.....	62
5.4 Machine Learning Model Development and Approach.....	65
5.6 Machine Learning Model Results	73
5.7 Results on Optimum Number of Student Clusters.....	73
5.8 Results from Predictive Models to Identify Student Groups	75
5.9 Exploring Evaluation Metrics for K-means.....	81
5.10 Chapter Summary	85
Chapter 6 STUDENT FEEDBACK, INTERVENTIONS AND RESULTS.....	86
6.1 Introduction.....	86
6.2 Dashboard Development Using Power BI.....	86
6.3 Personalised Automated Feedback	90
6.4 Design of Feedback.....	91
6.5 App Prototype Development for Feedback.....	96
6.6 Survey Design Using Microsoft Forms	96
6.7 Survey Results from the Student Feedback Survey.....	97
6.8 Chapter Summary	100
Chapter 7 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK.....	101
7.1 Introduction.....	101
7.2 Research Question Answers.....	102
7.3 Research Objectives and Achievements	104
7.4 Areas of Future Work.....	108
7.5 Chapter Summary	109
Bibliography	111

DEDICATION

I dedicate this work first to God almighty, whose guidance and protection helps me make the right choices in my life. I am also dedicating this work to my late father Mr. Joseph Nnabuife Ogbuchi, whose life, though short, was full of impact and continues to instruct me every day and to my mother, Mrs. Ngozi Clementina Ogbuchi, who provided me with the opportunity to pursue my education despite the challenges we faced after my father's passing.

I also dedicate this work to those who may be feeling lost or unsure of their path, who may have experienced moments of self-doubt and who may be facing seemingly insurmountable obstacles. I want to urge you to keep going even when it feels like all odds are stacked against you. Never give up on your dreams and continue to pursue what is right. Unexpected joys and opportunities will emerge when you least expect them. So, hold on tight!

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LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 3-1 The learning analytics framework proposed by Khalil and Ebner (2022).	32
Figure 3-2 Data components across the learning environment.	34
Figure 3-3 Data flow and tools used at each stage of the learning analytics framework.	35
Figure 4-1 ETL (Extract, Load, Transform) process flow.	43
Figure 4-2 Data cleaning process adapted from Quigley et al. (2021).	45
Figure 4-3 Boxplot of total interaction against pass/fail groups across all years.	49
Figure 4-4 Boxplot of average interactions per day for different student groups.	50
Figure 4-5 Boxplot of days between interactions for different student groups.	51
Figure 4-6 Boxplot of attendance against pass/fail groups across all datasets.	52
Figure 4-7 Histogram of log interactions for academic year by months.	54
Figure 4-8 Histogram of log interaction by day of the week.	55
Figure 4-9 Histogram of log interaction distribution by hour of the day.	56
Figure 4-10 Scatterplot of attendance against final grade across groups.	57
Figure 4-11 Correlation heatmap of selected features for MS2.	58
Figure 5-1 Summary of data analytics process.	61
Figure 5-2 Machine learning model development process.	66
Figure 5-3 Silhouette score graphs across all models tested.	73
Figure 5-4 Elbow method used to determine optimum number of clusters.	74
Figure 5-5 Distortion and silhouette metric scores for MC1 and MS.	75
Figure 5-6 Cluster patterns found across datasets using three clusters.	78
Figure 5-7 Cluster patterns found across datasets using two clusters.	79
Figure 5-8 Heatmap showing confusion matrices for MC3 and MS3.	84
Figure 6-1 Power BI dashboard developed to support intervention.	89
Figure 6-2 Preview of combined data after automated comments generated.	92
Figure 6-3 Connecting to Power Automate for email automation.	93
Figure 6-4 Customizing Power Automate to pick values from automation.	94
Figure 6-5 Personalised sample email sent out to students as an intervention step.	95
Figure 6-6 Word cloud of question 2 responses.	98
Figure 6-7 Sample comments on question 2.	99
Figure 6-8 Word cloud showing student preferences in receiving personalized feedback.	99
Figure 6-9 Word cloud showing how language used made students feel.	100

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1-1 Research objectives	15
Table 4-1 Datasets from the courses used for this study.....	38
Table 4-2 Summary description of Features in Datasets	39
Table 4-3 Total number of features in datasets for every activity type.....	41
Table 4-4 Descriptive statistics of selected features in dataset MS2 (n=241)	46
Table 4-5 Progression rates across all datasets.	47
Table 5-1 MI scores for MC1 Dataset.....	63
Table 5-2 K-means predictions using 3 clusters.	76
Table 5-3 K-means predictions using 2 clusters.	77
Table 5-4 Cluster validation evaluation results for MS1, MC1 for two 2 and 3 clusters.	81
Table 5-5 Week 5 model prediction evaluated across different metrics.	82
Table 5-6 Model evaluation for MC2 & MS2 at term end	82
Table 5-7 Model evaluation on MC3 and MS3 for 3 clusters at week 7	83

GLOSSARY

In this section, commonly used terms through the thesis are briefly described below:

Moodle: Moodle is an open-source learning management system (LMS) which is used by many educational institutions and businesses for creating and managing online courses in learning environments.

Virtual learning environment (VLE): VLEs are systems that facilitate online learning and education by providing a digital platform where such learning can take place. It also enables a platform on which courses, activities, and resources for education can easily be created and managed.

Data Mining: Data mining refers to a series of processes involved in uncovering patterns, useful insights, and trends in large datasets. It involves the use of different techniques and algorithms to analyse and extract useful information from data which is beneficial to decision-making. Data cleaning which refers to techniques for putting data in right format for analysis is also a data mining step.

Learning Analytics: Learning analytics is a field of study which involves processes for collecting and analysing data from educational environments with the aim of gaining a better understanding of student learning behaviours and discovering best practices to support them. It leverages data mining and technology to extract insightful information from data and to inform stakeholders and educators in education.

Features: In the context of building machine learning models, these refer to the characteristics of the given dataset, providing information about an instance of a given observation or row. It is also interchangeably referred to as columns or variables in other texts.

Clustering: Clustering in machine learning refers to the process of grouping similar data points in a dataset based on their respective features.

Machine Learning (ML): Machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence which involves the development of algorithms that enable computers learn from data and make predictions based on that learning without being explicitly programmed to do so.

Artificial Intelligence (AI): which make this possible.

Unsupervised Learning: In machine learning, unsupervised learning refers to a subtype in which the algorithm learns patterns from data fed into it without any supervision in the form of labelled outcomes. The system discovers patterns and groups inherent in the data without any labels.

Supervised Learning: This is quite the opposite of unsupervised learning, and in supervised learning, labelled outcomes are provided to the computer system, which learns patterns and relationships in the data related to the provided labels.

Target Feature: In supervised machine learning, target feature refers to the variable one is trying to predict or classify. It is known as the dependent variable which is influenced by all other variables in the dataset. In unsupervised learning, there is no target feature.

Stakeholders: These refer to the leaders and elected officials at the institution who are responsible for managing and overseeing the operations of the university, and who ensure students learn effectively in a positive learning environment. They are also responsible for setting policies and the effective allocation of resources to ensure that the university meets the learning needs and expectations of the students.

STUDENT DECLARATION

By inserting my name below, I declare that this material, which I now submit for assessment, is my own work, and that any assistance I received in its preparation is fully acknowledged and disclosed in the document. To the best of my knowledge and beliefs, all sources have been properly acknowledged, and the assessment task contained no plagiarism.

I understand that plagiarism, collusion, and/or copying is a grave and serious offence at the university and am aware that penalties could include a zero-mark, suspension, or expulsion from the institute.

I acknowledge that this assessment submission may be transferred and stored in a database for data matching to help detect plagiarism. I declare that this document was prepared by me for the purpose of complete fulfilment of requirements for the research master's degree programme I am registered on. I also declare that this assignment, or any part of it, has not been previously submitted by me or any other person for assessment of this or any other course of study, either at ATU Galway or at another university.

Signed: Ikechukwu Ogbuchi

Date: 6 December 2023

RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS

Analytics Team Award:

International Award from the Data Science and Machine Learning company Dataiku (Headquarters in New York, United States) under the Responsible AI category in 2022: <https://blog.dataiku.com/frontrunner-award-winners>

Open-Source Contribution:

The research has contributed to open-source development by creating an API on Moodle that can pull out attendance information from the learner database, the API created using Python Flask and shared on GitHub can be found on Moodle documentation page under the section “API to Pull Specific Attendance Information”:

https://docs.moodle.org/400/en/Attendance_activity

Publications

Ogbuchi, I., Kiely, E., Quigley, C., & McGinty, D. (2022). Exploring the use of machine learning to improve student engagement and retention. *ICERI2022 Proceedings*, 3385-3390. <https://doi.org/10.21125/iceri.2022.0828>

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ABSTRACT

Data-driven insights play a pivotal role in optimising learning analytics within higher education institutions. Despite their importance, much of the data in these institutions remains untapped, trapped in siloed data stores. This study addresses this challenge by applying machine learning and mathematical modelling using a learning analytics research framework (Khalil et al., 2022), encompassing phases of data insights, analytics, and intervention. The study aimed to identify features influencing learner progression and discover student groups in educational environments. Utilising data from 1,017 students over a 3-year period, the research employed unsupervised machine learning techniques and automated student feedback. Feature analysis identified attendance, interactions, time intervals, and activities related to quizzes and workshops as useful predictors of students requiring additional support. K-means model performs best with an average recall of 89% and an overall accuracy of 72% for identifying at-risk student groups using non-personally identifying data.

The findings emphasise the utility of unsupervised machine learning for early identification of at-risk students, enabling timely interventions to prevent potential failure or dropout. Personalised and automated feedback forms summarising students' progression received high ratings, 93% rating for usefulness from students, highlighting their satisfaction with it as a learning analytics intervention. Insights highlight the importance of data quality, personalised feedback, and transparent communication with learners. Challenges, such as automating feedback and scalability, are addressed, along with the necessity of leveraging non-personally identified data to mitigate bias.

The incorporation of a data science approach, enriched by machine learning, holds the potential to provide stakeholders with enriched insights, boost student engagement, and enhance overall student outcomes. This study will extend the body of knowledge of how machine learning modelling can be used to foster and promote student success in higher education.

Chapter 1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Learning analytics data is only valuable when it is transformed into a format which is interpretable and can provide actionable insights. This study investigates how machine learning algorithms and mathematical modelling can enable digital and learning transformation in Higher Education by identifying the factors affecting learners' success. The collective data of the ATU partners, with a student population of approximately 25,000, offers significant potential for very rich insights into existing and emerging patterns and trends in learner behaviour. However, it is important to note that this study focused on only a subset of this large dataset which is data from the School of Science and Computing within ATU consisting of 3 academic sessions involving 1,017 first year students. Measuring student engagement has proven difficult, and data collected from interactions with content, grades in activities, and online attendance are often siloed and inaccessible.

Due to increased learning on online learning platforms, a vast amount of data is generated as students interact with the learner content, and insights about the student's learning pattern can be derived and potential behaviour predicted. Student engagement is a crucial factor in learning outcomes in higher education (Boulton et al.2019). This study aims to explore how machine learning can be leveraged to improve student engagement. More specifically, the research aims to establish patterns in the Moodle VLE data to identify student groups based on their engagement with their courses and interactions.

This project involves three key aspects: (1) data mining and analysis, and (2) machine learning model development and (3) evaluation of personalised student feedback. This is targeted at extending the field of learning analytics (LA) by performing a sophisticated analysis of

learners' engagement in interconnected learning environments. Creating a protocol for assessing and relating student data will transform data into information, facilitating the second part of the project: visualisation and insights.

In the second part, the project explores the nonlinear relationships between factors that affect student success. Using anonymised historical data, this project applies selected machine learning algorithms to develop models to predict a student's success score and identify the factors contributing to student success. Features, such as student attendance, quiz participation, journal interaction, workshop practices, and interactions from assignments, were used to create these algorithms.

The adoption of a data-science approach, enhanced by machine learning, offers stakeholders greater insight, enhances student engagement, improves student outcomes, and facilitates operational improvements through real-time access to performance indicators.

1.2 Aim and Objectives

The aim of this study was to investigate how machine learning algorithms and mathematical modelling can inform and influence transformative learning in Higher Education.

At the end, interactive dashboards were created based on findings, to show predicted student categories and insights for stakeholders, educators, and learners.

Specifically, the research objectives are shown in Table 1-1:

Table 1-1 Research objectives

Objective 1:	Creation of a data pipeline and visualisation system for data ingestion and analysis.
Objective 2:	Exploring the application of machine learning (ML) technologies for learning analytics in higher education.
Objective 3:	Identify meaningful predictors for student success, using both real-time and historical data.
Objective 4:	Validate ML models and explore impact of personalised feedback.
Objective 5:	Extend the body of knowledge of applied machine learning in Irish and international higher education settings.

1.3 Central Research Questions:

The research aims to answer key research questions on the early indicators that can predict student success or disengagement, the patterns which can be uncovered from student interactions and online learning behaviour, and whether machine learning can predict, with good accuracy, students who are at risk. Specifically, the following:

- Can historical data (three years) uncover patterns and insights between successful and unsuccessful students based on their interactions and learning behaviour?
- Can machine learning models predict risk/struggling students with good accuracy?
What are the early indicators that predict students' success or disengagement?
- How effective is automated and personalised feedback forms as an intervention method within the learning analytics framework?

1.4 Limitations of Study

There are some limitations related to the research study, these include:

1. Datasets used for this study were from the School of Science and Computing within ATU Galway. The limited scope in this dataset might mean that results found may not be consistent across other faculties in the university. To ensure it is generalisable, other datasets from other faculties need to be explored to ensure results will be consistent before wide adoption. It will also offer more comprehensive understanding of student behaviour across other academic disciplines.
2. The study involved evaluation of a few machine learning models due to resource and time constraints. Although exploring commonly applied models in learning analytics offer good promise, it is important to investigate the less conventional models which could offer valuable insights into their potential relevance in learning analytics and assess their performance.
3. Interaction data extracted from the log files used for this study were generally aggregated using the frequency count from all activity types per student. Breaking down this data into more granular groups has the potential to reveal more patterns in student engagement that could impact learning outcomes. Further research could benefit from this deeper exploration to uncover potentially significant insights.
4. This research focused exclusively on data generated within the institution by the student excluding any third-party or sensitive data related to the student. This decision was mainly driven by the ethical considerations surrounding data privacy, protection, and confidentiality. While using data from these other sources may enhance the depth of the research, there are still challenges that come with navigating the privacy concerns.

1.5 Thesis Structure

This thesis consists of seven chapters. The first chapter, the introduction chapter, provides an overview of the aims and objectives, pertinent research questions, and term definition, and offers a preliminary exploration of what is expected in the subsequent chapters.

The second chapter is the literature review chapter which critically evaluates, and benchmarks research works that have been undertaken in the field of learning analytics. It also aims to give the reader the rationale behind this thesis topic and the gaps identified in previous works which are explored here.

The third chapter delves into the methodology of the processes and mechanisms employed to answer the research questions. It introduces the methodology framework chosen for this research, the learning environment, and the next three chapters which deal with methodologies associated with each of the research questions.

The fourth chapter focuses on the methodology used to uncover patterns and behaviours in the learner data. It addresses the methodology, results, and insights related to the first research question. This was explored using visualisations, dataset descriptions, and tables. It also presents the findings from the data analysis related to the first research question.

The fifth chapter reports the methodology and results derived from the application of machine learning techniques in this research. Statistical feature selection techniques, machine learning modelling to identify student groups, and the rationale for model choice were explored, answering the second research question.

Chapter 6 focuses on the methodology and results of the third research question. It reports on how the personalised feedback forms sent to the students were developed, and how survey forms were developed to capture what the students thought about the feedback received and results from both processes. It also reports on the mechanisms used to compare the effects of student feedback as an intervention step, using statistical tests on their interactions.

Chapter 7 ties it together and discusses key findings based on results and methodology, while offering conclusions, limitations of the study and considers possible areas for future research.

Chapter 2 LITERATURE REVIEW

In this chapter, the background literature related to this thesis is reviewed across different domains, and the research gaps are identified.

2.1 Learning Analytics, Student Engagement and Success

Student engagement is a key factor in student success, and learning analytics can be a powerful tool to improve student success. The working definition of learning analytics according to Long & Siemens (2011) is the measurement, collection, analysis, and reporting of data about learners and their contexts for purposes of understanding and optimising learning and the environments in which it occurs. Learning analytics is an evolving, multidisciplinary research field that requires skills and input from various researchers and disciplines. It is critical that the science of learning and curriculum design is kept at the heart of the analytics solution, recognising educators and students as key stakeholders and beneficiaries of learning analytics (Tsai et al., 2018).

“Learning analytics can reveal a lot about the progress of learners and the suitability of the contexts in which learning takes place. Employed intelligently, it can supply predictive models that can inform pedagogical approaches; it can inform earlier and more focused student interventions; and it can act as an evidence base for quality assurance and enhancement” (Lee O’Farrell, 2017).

Some education programs suffer high attrition rates, primarily due to the poor engagement of students with their classes. According to O’Brien, (2022) lower attendance rates and poor student engagement are among the current academic concerns. Farag (2020) noted the high rate of attrition in the freshman year for an engineering programme. These challenges are primarily due to the poor engagement of students in their classes. Research conducted by Hu

et al. (2016) show that there is little research on learning analytics based on student engagement online, emphasizes its importance and the necessity of further research on this as it pertains to student learning. Mohd et al., (2016) found that student engagement in learning correlates with good academic results which implies success and researchers Hu et al. (2021) also found that student engagement is an important indicator of the effects of learning in higher education.

Yoong (2014) proposes that to improve student learning, there is a need to better understand students and analyse the data tracked from student learning activities online. One way in which learning analytics can be used to improve student engagement is by tracking student activity and completion. Anthony (2021) found that tracking activities and completion is useful to improve student engagement. An educator can use learning analytics to track how often students access course materials, complete assignments, or quizzes, and participate in discussions. This information could then be used to identify students who are at risk of disengaging and to provide them with the required support.

Developing environments and tools to track these activities is useful in learning analytics. Pérez-Berenguer et al. (2016) highlighted the benefit of developing environments to track these learning activities as a way of improving learning analytics. Therefore, developing learning management systems and technology tools which track student activities and provide instructors with reports on student engagement is a valuable way of implementing learning analytics.

Learning analytics, an evolving research field, can help enhance the field of education and student success through more informed and focused interventions. It can be used to understand the relationships between students, educators, and their subject matter (O'Farrell, 2017).

Learning analytics can be used to support at-risk students. Katerina et al. (2019) showed that learning analytics can support data-driven learning design when data are collected from various sources and come from a regular part of the students' learning process. Hongxin (2020) highlighted in a research paper that learning analytics can be used to support at-risk students in an institution. An institution can use learning analytics to identify students at risk of dropping out and provide them with additional support services. Learning analytics, although still a young field, is a powerful resource for informed decision making and better learning outcomes. Flores-Vivar & García-Peñalvo (2022) described how artificial intelligence (AI) in education can be useful to both students and educators. AI can be used as a tool in learning analytics to identify student groups such as those at risk of dropping out and to support students who learn differently.

Research findings from Nurfadhlina et al. (2021) measured student engagement using learning analytics and concluded that course participation and achievement have a strong positive correlation. Although these studies have shown the usefulness of learning analytics and its value, there have been challenges in implementing it across educational institutions and deriving the greatest value. Tsai & Gasevic (2017) noted that there are technical, organisational, and pedagogical challenges that come with learning analytics. One of them is the limited availability of policies tailored for learning analytics which address issues such as privacy; there are also a limited number of studies empirically validating the impact of learning analytics intervention. Challenges have also been identified in how to use it and how it can be best applied (Banihashem et al., 2018).

2.2 Artificial Intelligence, Blended Learning and Learning Analytics

AI and machine learning are critical technologies used to enhance learning. Kuleto et al. (2021) showed that the use of analytics and AI can help universities mitigate challenges that come with teaching students and design a curriculum that meets their needs. Waheed et al. (2020) highlighted that machine learning algorithms can be used to make predictions for at-risk university students from VLEs. According to Kew et al. (2017), the identification of learning indicators is of great importance, as it enhances the prediction and identification of at-risk students. Mireilla (2017) highlights the importance of tracking digital footprint data on students' interaction with their feedback to identify students at risk of failing a module. These research findings demonstrate the relevance of technological tools in learning analytics.

Student engagement as a vital construct in understanding student learning behaviour could be used in evaluating technology-enhanced learning systems on their ability to properly impact students' learning. Fidelia et al. (2022) demonstrated that student engagement data are good indicators of academic performance and learning. By integrating learning analytics into the blended learning process, students' learning can be better understood and promoted (Baolin, 2017). Mark (2021) revealed that all students and not just at-risk students could benefit from interventions informed by learning analytics, and research findings explored by Tuti (2020) show that predictive models leveraging machine learning methods are effective in the exploratory data analytics of student data.

Based on these, there is a need for greater digital measures of student success post covid through blended learning. Blended learning refers to a learning method which combines the traditional face-to-face learning style with online or e-activities (Attard & Holmes, 2022). This

mode of learning is essential for providing institutions with a data source which can be used to harness the power of learning analytics. Adiguzel et al. (2020) found benefits of using digital products in student courses and saw the future potential of blended learning products in the overall teaching and learning experience of students.

2.3 Learning Analytics and Machine Learning

The adoption of learning analytics enhanced by machine learning may offer stakeholders greater insight and enhance student engagement, thereby improving student outcomes and facilitating operational improvements through real-time access to key performance indicators. Machine Learning also referred to as ML is a branch of artificial intelligence (AI) and computer science which focuses on the use of data and algorithms to imitate the way that humans learn, gradually improving its accuracy (IBM, 2022).

“AI and machine learning are critical technologies for enhancing learning, primarily through students’ skills, collaborative learning in HEIs, enhancing the security and efficiency of the institution, and providing a conducive research environment.” (Kuleto et al., 2021)

Educational institutions store massive amounts of student data that are often left unanalysed for insights. Machine learning holds significant value for big data generated by educational institutions. Machine learning uses programming and mathematical tools to learn patterns in data, which are often difficult to discover. The types of Machine Learning include supervised, unsupervised, reinforcement learning, semi-supervised learning, and learning-to-learn (Oladipupo, 2010). Supervised learning techniques focus on teaching computers how to learn from data by showing what they should look out for. In unsupervised learning, the data are fed into the model through programming, and the model automatically identifies the patterns in the

data without necessarily being shown what to identify. In reinforcement learning, the model is trained using a reward system, whereby it acts in an environment and is penalised or rewarded according to the set of actions it takes.

Studies have shown that student dropout rates are increasing across various institutions, and concerns have been raised over low student engagement (O'Brien, 2022). This is a growing concern, as the government has earmarked a large amount of funding for education. Since 2016, there has been significant public reinvestment in higher education of €1.1 billion by the government, an increase of over 40% (Department of Further and Higher Education, 2022). Increased spending on education aims to create a high-quality learning environment for students and equip them for national development. However, student dropout rates are increasing (Dass et al., 2021).

Dass et al. (2021) considered the following features in predicting student performance: time and topics, topics mastered, topics practiced, and time spent. Daud et al. (2017) noted in their work that the ability to predict whether a student will be successful or not is an interesting area because it could provide educational institutions with useful knowledge from their databases. This is important as it can aid institutions in making quick decisions about their students before they decide to quit through additional support or simply adapt them to a favourable teaching style. Daud et al. (2017) used information on family expenditure (electricity bills, gas bills, medical expenditure, accommodation spend.), family income (father income, mother income, personal income, miscellaneous income etc.) student personal information (gender, marital status, home ownership, previous institutions attended) and family assets (land value, stock value, house value, value of vehicle assets) to predict student performance as a way of supporting analytics. However, the work acknowledged that in most of the cases, not all these

data were available for a dynamic construction of the student identity. Access to some of this information is also dependent on the student's willingness to share them. Omar et al. (2020) applied a clustering approach for analysing student efficiency and performance using just the grade and the GPA value in their dataset.

Nafuri et al. (2022) used clustering analysis to classify student academic performance in higher education using gender, registration age, marital status, place of birth, income status, entry qualification, sponsorship, residence, Curriculum Grade Point Average (CGPA) and employment status as predictors. Gray (2015) has been well cited in the field of learning analytics for the application of machine learning. It is thorough work exploring learner motivation, age relationship with performance, and self-efficacy. However, personal information relating to the student, such as age, gender, and course of study, were used as features. The study however found that these factors were not indicative or significant in creating classification models of students at risk of failing. Embarak (2020) also applied machine learning to predict students at risk using only high school math SAT score, the English SAT score and high school grade. Although the study found good correlation between the features used and their eventual performance, it acknowledged discrepancies found between learners in different programs.

In all these studies, there has been an element of using personal information for model development. This means that existing attempts to predict student performance and inform learning analytics have somehow been influenced by a student's past, the gender they identify with, or the family circumstances they have been in.

2.4 Student Feedback and Learning Analytics

Student feedback plays a crucial role in supporting learners' development (Gómez-Chova, 2023). Acevedo et al. (2018) assert that providing personalised feedback to students and educators is one of the possible objectives of Learning analytics while also highlighting prediction and recommendation as other goals. Student feedback has also been shown to be an important factor in supporting student success and shows the need for new approaches to establish connections between student data and its usage for providing high-quality feedback (Pardo et al., 2019). The use of learning analytics to provide this feedback highlights a gap that needs to be investigated. Recommendation and guidance feedback based on learning analytics will provide important opportunities for students with low self-directed learning skills (Karaoglan Yilmaz & Yilmaz, 2020).

According to Şahin & Yurdugül (2019), interventions are conducted through feedback. Feedback is also discussed as a useful intervention in educational settings and its use as an intervention step has been observed to show statistical differences in academic achievement, favouring students who received feedback over those who did not (Ezin & Yilmaz, 2022). Although significant efforts have been made towards automating feedback generation, Rabelo et al. (2023) highlighted that relatively little attention has been paid to the design of feedback and its personalisation.

Henderson et al. (2019) found that feedback as an intervention step needs to be understood as it is a complex process influenced by different factors. The research also highlighted that the major barriers to providing students with well-crafted and personalised feedback were lack of time and scalability issues. In providing feedback to students, there are practical issues with getting the staff to be consistent with their comments and issuing guidance to students on how

they can improve their performance while doing this in a way that saves time and energy, especially in large classrooms (Biggam, 2010).

The insights from these research articles have guided the development of a simple and automated student feedback mechanism to provide feedback to students.

2.5 Data Protection in Learning Analytics

Although there is a growing interest in learning analytics, its applications in the field of education and its potential in supporting student success has raised data privacy considerations. These surround the adoption and acceptability of different approaches to learning analytics, especially regarding data ownership (Drachler & Greller, 2016). Research has also shown that current attempts to address data management issues in learning analytics are currently coming in the form of frameworks which are designed as guide codes of practice for different stakeholders in educational institutions (Pardo & Siemens, 2014). There is a need to establish standards regarding data used in learning analytics. Learning analytics teams must analyse how these standards are implemented and how the different data protection concerns across the board are met (Hoel & Chen, 2016).

Frameworks are useful instruments to structure the discussions geared towards a more robust application of learning analytics which can meet educational standards. Therefore, there is a need for data policies in learning institutions to establish broad frameworks for secure, fair, and compliant data governance (Petersen, 2012). Designing systems that efficiently collect data at every step of the student learning journey can address student needs through feedback which

can promote richer and better learning. Good learning management, reliable data warehousing, safeguarded data privacy and management of secure access to data have all been highlighted as ways of addressing the contemporary challenges with data handling and privacy (Daniel, 2015).

Recent research has also shown that strong stakeholder engagement in a university and proper understanding of how their data (from the institution) are used leads to higher quality data and produces more beneficial outcomes for the university (García-Peñalvo, 2020). In a study by McNicol et al. (2023), questions were raised by end-users who focused on the transparency of the processes associated with collection, storage, and usage of data related to a proposed data framework which was built based on an evidence-based need for increased transparency and engagement by end-users. They found that transparency and user engagement are trademarks for recent initiatives in the field of data governance.

This research ensured that the data were handled in a secure manner, meeting the data protection standards set by the data protection and IT departments. Additional steps were taken to obtain informed consent from the participating students and to ensure that none of their personally identifiable information was used to build predictive models. None of these previous works have made predictions solely based on how students interact and engage with their course content and materials. The research team contributed to the development of ATU Learning Analytics Student Success Policy and worked closely with the DPIA office to ensure compliance with up-to-date Data Protection Policy.

2.6 Gaps Identified

The gap here is to explore the potential of using non-personally identifying data in the prediction of student success in the Irish university setting. Identifying at-risk students based only on their patterns of interaction and engagement with their learning materials, with a high level of accuracy, will mitigate the potential chances of introducing bias to our predictive models. This bias could come unintentionally from personal information related to gender, ethnicity, family background, or education history. This means that the predictive models can begin to learn using bias-prone patterns like “people from a particular ethnic group” are more likely to fail a course or that people from a family income threshold are more likely to fail. An example of such forms of bias as relates to gender is discussed by Mehmood et al. (2022) which also highlighted the importance of considering different aspects of this form of bias which currently are seldom discussed. This study is the first to explore the power of predictive models (using machine learning) for improving learning analytics using only data from student interaction with their course components.

Using readily available data regarding learner behaviour in building predictive models holds significant value, as opposed to relying on historical personal data outside the institution, which may lead to bias. The challenges with obtaining such data also highlight the need for developing models solely considering data generated from student activity within their course. Machine-learning analytics can be used to explore this gap. The primary goal of analytics according to Chatti et al. (2012) is exploring the value of data gathered in providing learning professionals, and students, with actionable information that could be used to enhance the learning environment. Dawson et al. (2014) proposed that the application of data analytics in educational settings is a rapidly growing research discipline. This leads to exploring the VLE platform Moodle to obtain insights and make predictions about students who could be at risk.

2.7 Literature Review Summary

The reviewed literature highlights the important role of learning analytics in understanding and optimising learning environments, particularly as it relates to student engagement and success. Analytics are useful for tracking and enhancing engagement which can address high attrition rates. The application of machine learning in this field equips educational institutions with predictive capabilities that can be useful in identifying at-risk students and improving learning outcomes.

Blended learning has also been highlighted as a valuable source of meaningful data for learning analytics. However, challenges persist in automating personalised feedback and addressing scalability issues. Data handling and protection are also a critical area, as there are many ongoing discussions surrounding the right use of data, the need for strong data governance, collective engagement, and strict adherence to data frameworks for data use.

To address the gaps identified in the literature review, this research focuses on leveraging non-personally identified data to predict student success, with the aim of mitigating bias in predictive models. It also focuses on exploring unsupervised learning approaches, which are not commonly applied in this area.

This chapter explores the evolving landscape of learning analytics and machine learning in education. It advocates the need for strict data practices, while also emphasising the need for new approaches to building predictive models. All of this is aimed at a more accurate and fair application of technology to optimise learning analytics.

Chapter 3 METHODOLOGY OVERVIEW

3.1 Introduction

This chapter gives an overview of the methodology framework followed for the research which guides the methodology in the following chapters. It begins with describing the methodology framework chosen and the rationale for it. It then dives into the four components of the chosen framework which consists of: the learning environment, data, analytics, and action phases. It focuses on the learning environment component, while the next three chapters focus on the other aspects.

The following research questions guide the methodology followed through all the chapters:

1. Can historical data (three years) uncover patterns and insights into student interactions and learning behaviour?
2. Can machine learning models identify features that predict at-risk students with good accuracy?
3. How effective is automated feedback an intervention method?

3.2 Methodology Framework

Before deciding on the appropriate methods to answer the research questions, there was a need to choose an effective framework to guide the choice of methods and steps to be taken therein. It has been found from a critical analysis of learning analytics frameworks that valuable theoretical and pedagogical guidelines for educators already exist (Kaliisa et al., 2022). A systematic review found a broad consensus on the core elements of learning analytics frameworks, which encompass development, application, privacy, representation, data source, data type, focus/purpose, and educational context (Khalil et al., 2022).

A pictorial representation of the chosen framework is shown in Figure 3-1 below which visually shows its constituents and considerations. It also includes details on how it revolves around learners, processes, data interpretation, optimisation and some of the components involved in each stage of the framework.

Figure 3-1 The learning analytics framework proposed by Khalil and Ebner (2022).

The goal of this framework is to enhance learning and lead to well-informed decision making in education institutions.

Based on the design goals formulated from reviewing existing literature, the framework used for this research is based on the learning analytics framework proposed by Khalil & Ebner, (2015) and Clow (2012) which consist of four key parts:

1. Learning Environment: This refers to the environment that produces data and everything constituting this environment. Clow referred to this part as “Learners” in his framework.

2. **Big Data:** This is a diverse collection of datasets captured from the learning environment. This data cuts across interactions, grades, learning activities, and academic information. Referred to as the “Data” phase in the Clow framework.
3. **Analytics:** Different data analysis methods are employed to identify trends, patterns, and derive insights. Qualitative and quantitative data are analysed using statistics and are visualised. Predictive models are employed in this phase. Clow called this the “Metric” phase.
4. **Action:** This is the phase in which the results from the analysis are used to improve the learning environment. It includes steps taken to intervene, personalisation of learning and change of learning policies to improve the learner experience. This stage is called “Intervention” in the Clow framework.

3.3 Learning Environment

This research involved data from a pilot group of students at the Atlantic Technological University (ATU), obtained from the primary virtual learning environment for their course content, which was Moodle. A virtual learning environment (VLE) is akin to a digital classroom accessible over the internet and where educators can share their lectures, assignments, and learning resources with students. Students can access this learning environment through their phones, laptops, or tablet devices. It also enables seamless and real-time communication between students and their educators, offering them the flexibility to learn anywhere. Moodle is an open source VLE (publicly and freely available for use) designed to help educators create effective online course content for students.

The learning environment was also integrated with the Microsoft Cloud platform (Azure) which provides a wide range of services for different applications. Microsoft Cloud supports

student sign-in to their courses using institute email login credentials and grants them access to securely download educational software. The platform also supports an automated feedback system which can be used as an intervention step. This environment also supports the tools used in other parts of this framework.

1. Microsoft Power Automate: an automation tool that supports the automation of repetitive activities on the Microsoft Cloud platform.
2. Microsoft Power BI: an analytics tool that enables visualisation of data for insights and creation of dashboards.

Figure 3-2 illustrates different data components across the learning environment and how they interact with each other.

Figure 3-2 Data components across the learning environment.

The learning environment consists of software integrated from different systems within the institution and the reporting tools used. Data on student interaction and activities is generated

from this environment. Some of the software used are Moodle, Microsoft Teams, Office Suite and SharePoint.

The Microsoft Cloud platform also supports the development environment for this project which was primarily Jupyter Notebooks. Jupyter Notebook is an interactive computing environment in which computer code can be written and executed within cells. It supports different programming languages, but for this research, the programming language used was Python. Figure 3-3 illustrates the components of how data for the research was extracted from the learning environment and the tools used at each stage of the chosen learning analytics framework. It shows data extracted from the virtual learning environment stored in a database and the data cleaning and analytics phases (which were supported by virtual servers and visualisation tools). It also shows how insights and findings from the data phase were integrated within the Microsoft cloud platform Azure, from which intervention in the form of personalised feedback was designed.

Figure 3-3 Data flow and tools used at each stage of the learning analytics framework.

Chapters 4 through 6 discuss the data, insights, and intervention phases of the chosen methodology framework from the learning environment. They are broken down as follows:

- Chapter 4 (Data and part Analytics Phase) – This explores research question 1.
- Chapter 5 (Analytics Phase – Predictive) – Explores research question 2.
- Chapter 6 (Intervention Phase) – Explores research question 3.

3.4 Data Protection Steps

Based on the literature reviewed regarding data protection, the following considerations and guidelines were followed prior to data analysis, these are also outlined in the learning analytics policy document of the institution:

1. The research ensured strict compliance with the data governance structure at the institution managed by the data protection office.
2. Clear guidelines on data collection, storage and usage were established. Ensuring that data was retrieved and conveniently stored on a system approved by the institution for analysis.
3. Transparency in the usage of the data across the learning analytics team was followed.
4. Informed consent was obtained from the student groups who participated in the pilot study both digitally and in classrooms, students were also aware of the purpose behind the research.
5. Measures were taken to prevent algorithmic bias by only including data generated from student learning for model development and not retrieving or including data related to demographics.
6. Latest guidelines and policies regarding data protection at the university were continuously reviewed and followed in alignment with the continuously evolving data protection norms and GDPR regulations.

Chapter 4 DATA INSIGHTS AND PATTERNS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter answers the first research question which aims to uncover insights into student learning and interactions with their math modules based on the data captured. It focuses on the data phase of the learning analytics framework, which explored the datasets used, the descriptions of those datasets, the data extraction process, data processing, and tools used. Descriptive statistics of the data were explored, and comparisons of insights were made across the 3 years using visualisations. It also extends into the analytical phase of the framework to explore early insights.

4.2 Datasets Used for this Research

Datasets from three academic sessions with first-year students participating in a math module were used in this research study. The participating students were from the science and computing departments and gave their consent for the data to be used for this purpose.

Table 4-1 shows a summary of the datasets from the 3-year period with the number of participants in each year and aliases which will be used to refer to the datasets and the two groups involved which were science and computing.

Table 4-1 Datasets from the courses used for this study.

Year	Module	Alias	Number of Participants (n)
2020 - 2021	Essential Maths for Computing	MC1	106
2020 - 2021	Mathematics 1.1 for science	MS1	202
2021-2022	Essential Maths for Computing	MC2	132
2021-2022	Mathematics 1.1 for science	MS2	241
2022 – 2023	Essential Maths for Computing	MC3	122
2022-2023	Mathematics 1.1 for science	MS3	214
	Total		1017

Log file data for all the datasets were also extracted. The log files data contained time series information on the interactions the students had with different components of their courses. It was used to get information on how engaged the students were on the course from a time perspective. Data was extracted twice for the MC2, MS2 at week 5 of the course and at week 12. Data was also extracted twice at week 7 and week 12 of the semester for MC3 and MS3. It was only extracted once for the MC1, MC2 datasets as the course had already been completed at the time of beginning the analysis.

4.3 Datasets Description

The datasets used in this research were extracted from the Moodle VLE in a structured form. These ranged between 71 to 103 features each. The rows represented feature observations for

individual students. In all the datasets, there are five preceding features with only basic student details: name (first and last name), ID number, email address, and department. Those features were only used for identification purposes that facilitated the automated intervention and were not included in the analytics or modelling. The remaining features contained information about student activity records in the areas of assignments, quizzes, attendance, journals, grades, workshops, and completion checklists. Interaction data from the log files were also extracted and integrated with the datasets.

The features are listed in Table 4-2:

Table 4-2 Summary description of Features in Datasets

Feature type	Description
Quiz	Features associated with this represent quiz performance of the student across different quizzes and stored as a numeric value.
Attendance	Attendance captures the students available and participation during either their general lecture or journal classes.
Journal	Features associated with journal represent students journal performance. Journals are hands on classes where students are guided to complete work for each week related to topic taught during the week.
Grades	This feature represents the overall grade of the student as reflected by an aggregation of performance across different topics.
Assignments	This represents features in dataset that shows assignment completion rates for the students in group.
Workshops	Represents scores from workshop (group) activities assigned to the students.

Feature type	Description
Exams	These represent exam scores for the various exams taken by the students at different times in the semester.
Checklists	This feature represents the task completion checklist progress for course.
Interactions	These are captured from the log files and give an aggregated count of the number of interactions the student made on the learner platform in the form of clicks.
Average interactions per session	These represent the aggregated number of interactions per session when students logged on. This takes into consideration only the days when the student logged into to the course.
Average interactions per day	The average number of interactions per day for each student which takes into consideration all the days in the semester including those when there was no log in activity.
Days between interactions	The average time in days between clicks aggregated from the time stamps in the log files.

Table 4-3 presents a breakdown of the datasets and their total number of features for each activity type. The totals exclude the six features for identification, and four features aggregated from log files. The table shows the number of features in each activity category for each dataset.

Table 4-3 Total number of features in datasets for every activity type

Dataset	Assignment	Attendance	Grade	checklists	Exam	Journal	Quiz	Workshop	Total
MC1	2	2	1	1	2	10	25	18	61
MS1	0	2	1	1	4	10	25	20	63
MC2	22	2	1	1	4	10	27	18	85
MS2	20	2	1	1	3	10	26	20	83
MC3	3	2	2	1	4	11	27	18	68
MS3	8	3	2	1	2	10	27	40	93

Before the data analysis and model development, the data were cleaned and pre-processed. Feature selection technique was used prior to developing models. The technique used is explained in chapter 5.

4.4 Data Extraction Process

Data for model development were manually extracted from Moodle and application programming interfaces (APIs). APIs allow different applications to communicate with one another. It acts as a bridge which allows various programs to communicate and exchange information. The manual method of extraction involved logging into the Moodle platform with admin privileges for educators and downloading the gradebook and log file datasets. APIs were developed to enable an easier transfer of information from Moodle to the Jupyter Notebook environment without requiring manual extraction. An API was shared with the open-source

community to assist fellow researchers with extracting data from the Moodle database. The API which can extract attendance information can be found at

https://docs.moodle.org/402/en/Attendance_activity

Subsequently, the data were processed and cleaned. Log-file data were merged with course data to explore interaction relationships. This was achieved using software development tools, such as Power BI, the Python Merge function, and Excel. The data extraction process from the learning environment to the point where it is cleaned and loaded for analysis is known as ETL. ETL refers to Extract, Transform and Load. The following steps were taken during the data extraction process.

1. Administrator login to the data sources: Administrator permissions for access to the courses where the data was stored was initially granted. This facilitated the downloading of the course grade and log files from the settings on the course page. Data from Microsoft Forms which were obtained from the surveys were downloaded from the form page securely.
2. The data was then loaded into the Jupyter Notebook environment. Python libraries (collections of codes that make tasks more efficient) were required to load the data, transform it, and process it. The Pandas library was used for this purpose. Pandas provide different functions for reading data from various sources and transforming them into suitable formats. The NumPy library was also used for this purpose, as Pandas is built on top of it. It supports numerical computing and uses a large collection of mathematical functions to work on data structures.
3. Once the data have been extracted and pre-processed, it was stored using cloud-based services and ready for analysis.

Figure 4 -1 below shows the data flow during the Extract, Transform and Load processes. Data were extracted from the Moodle, log files, and the cloud environment. Subsequently, programming techniques and software are used to transform the data into a suitable form through transformation processes such as: renaming features, joining, or aggregation.

Figure 4-1 ETL (Extract, Load, Transform) process flow.

4.5 Data Processing

Data processing is important to ensure that the data used in the data phase of the learning analytics framework are of the appropriate format. It involves cleaning data and transforming it into a suitable format. Features with many missing values (>90%) were excluded from the data, as this would not be useful for the machine learning model to learn from. The decision to drop features of data with 90% or more missing values came from a review of common and standard approach practices in data analysis (Ngueilbaye et al., 2021).

Dropping features that have all missing values according to McKinney (2013) is a good approach. Research findings by Pratama et al. (2017) postulates that deletion is conventional technique for handling missing values. While deletion is a common practice, researchers Emmanuel et al. (2021) found by comparing various methods of handling missing data, more work is needed to explore new methods, as there are no clear indications that favour one method over another. There is a lot of ongoing research on various methods of handling features with missing values; removing features with over 90% missing values was considered a good approach in this case. Discarding features with a lot of missing values which aren't important features is also a good approach (Marcelino et al., 2022).

There were other features with missing values that still contained significant information. These features were retained, and the missing values were replaced with zero values.

Figure 4-2 illustrates the data cleaning process and its importance (Quigley et al., 2021). Data were entered as input through the learner management system in the form of activity scores, logs, and grades. The validation and verification of the data followed, and an output of clean and reliable data ready for analysis was generated.

Why Clean Data is Important

The quality of data input will be reflected in the information that can be gleaned from it.
Garbage in, garbage out.
Analysis of clean data must produce consistent results.

Figure 4-2 Data cleaning process adapted from Quigley et al. (2021).

4.6 Data Visualisation Overview

After the data was extracted and cleaned, it was visualised to explore the distribution and correlation of the selected features. Data visualisation is an essential component of the learning analytics framework. Various visualisation techniques, such as pair plots, scatter plots, line graphs, histograms, pie charts, box plots, 3D scatter plots, heatmaps, and bar graphs, were employed to present the data in a visually appealing and interpretable manner. These visualisations provided a comprehensive understanding of the data from different perspectives to the end user.

4.7 Descriptive Statistics

To gain insight into the relevant features in the cleaned data, descriptive statistics about the features in the datasets were performed. Table 4-3 shows some descriptive statistics for individual features selected from the activity types for the MC1 dataset.

Table 4-3 Descriptive statistics of selected features in dataset MC1

	Attendance	Checklist	Quiz Total	Workshop	Journal Total	Average Grade	Total Interactions
count	106	106	106	106	106	106	106
mean	69.6	84.1	70.0	72.7	69.5	87.8	1217.3
Standard deviation	32.6	30.2	32.7	42.6	36.6	30.5	526.7
min	0	0	0	0	0	0	15

Similar values were obtained for the MC2 and MC3 datasets within computing groups. For the science group, Table 4-4 shows a sample of descriptive statistics for MS2.

Table 4-4 Descriptive statistics of selected features in dataset MS2 (n=241)

	Attendance	Checklist	Journal Total	Quiz Total	Maths Grade	Days Between Interactions	Total Interactions
count	241	241	241	241	241	241	241
mean	54.2	58.1	9.9	6.7	43.7	4.0	1059.0
Standard deviation	26.1	35.9	6.8	5.4	28.1	4.2	684.6
min	0	0	0	0	0	1.4	3

Statistical descriptions of the selected features for MS2 were also similar in the MS1 and MS3 computing groups. Descriptive statistics for all datasets were computed using the Python

Describe function which computes the mean, median, standard deviation, and the maximum and minimum values across all selected features.

Progression rates across all datasets grouped by students who passed and failed were created as shown in Table 4-5. Progression rates fluctuate across the computing and science group, but there were improvements in MS3 and MC3.

Table 4-5 Progression rates across all datasets.

Dataset	Passed	Failed	Progression rate
MC1	82	24	77.36%
MS1	141	61	69.80%
MC2	91	41	68.94%
MS2	143	98	59.34%
MC3	86	36	70.49%
MS3	156	58	72.90%

4.9 Exploratory Data Visualisation and Insights

Exploratory data visualisation was performed on the cleaned data using various charts to derive insights and find patterns in the data phase of learning analytics. A feature was created to group the students into those who passed or failed the course based on the grade feature. The grouping was performed on the basis that any student who made a final grade of 40 or above was successful and those who did not, failed. After the feature was created, the following visuals were used to visualise the relationships and derive insights:

1. Box Plots were used explore relationships between students who passed or failed and other features from logs such as the Average interactions per day and total interactions.

2. Histograms were used to preview the student interaction behaviour on a monthly, weekly, and daily basis.
3. Line plots and scatter plots were used to compare relationships between selected features in the datasets.
4. Correlation plots were used to compare features against one another.

4.9.1 Visualisations and Insights using Boxplots

Relationships between log file interactions were explored using boxplots across total interactions, average daily interactions, average interactions per day, attendance, and the average number of days between interactions across all datasets.

Figure 4-3 shows boxplots of the total number of interactions across all the datasets. Box plot visualisations of total interactions showed that the majority of students who passed, interacted between 1000 and 2000 times, whereas the students who were unsuccessful in the course interacted between 0 and 1000 times. This was observed across all the years, as shown in Figure 4-3.

Figure 4-3 Boxplot of total interaction against pass/fail groups across all years.

Figure 4-4 shows boxplots of the average interactions per day across all the datasets. The feature representing the average interactions per day was derived from the total interactions, which is why the boxplots are similar. However, the derived feature shows that the majority of

students who passed the course interacted about four to seven times every day in the academic year, whereas most of the students who failed interacted about 0-3 times each day.

Figure 4-4 Boxplot of average interactions per day for different student groups.

Figure 4-5 depicts a boxplot of the days between interactions for student groups across all datasets. Most students who passed the module had an average of 2 to 4 days between their

interactions within the virtual learning environment. This contrasts with the majority of students in groups that failed, who had an average of about 3 to 7 days between interactions within their VLE.

Figure 4-5 Boxplot of days between interactions for different student groups.

Boxplots were also used to visualise the relationship between attendance and those students who passed or failed, as shown in Figure 4-6.

Figure 4-6 Boxplot of attendance against pass/fail groups across all datasets.

The results showed that the majority of students who passed the course had an attendance between 45% and 100%, whereas most of the students who failed had attendance below 60%.

4.9.2 Histogram: Visualisation and Insights

Histograms were used to explore the interactions using timestamps from the logs. The following insights were derived from these visuals.

Figure 4-7 shows the distribution of log file interactions across each month of the academic year. The results show similar trends over all datasets, with the highest interactions occurring in October, when the semester begins. It also shows a dip in January due to the Christmas holiday break period and weeks before resumption.

Figure 4-7 Histogram of log interactions for academic year by months.

Fig 4-8 shows the distribution of log interactions across days of the week. The results showed the least interactions during the weekends and maximum interactions on Monday for MC1, MC2, and Wednesday for the rest of the datasets.

Figure 4-8 Histogram of log interaction by day of the week.

Finally, histograms were used to explore the hourly interactions of the students. Figure 4-9 shows the results of the visualisation. The results showed that the majority of student interactions occurred between 9am and 4pm, with the fewest interactions occurring between

12:00 and 9:00am. The highest points also correlated with the hours when the students' attended lectures or journal classes, which is also when they take their exams or quizzes.

Figure 4-9 Histogram of log interaction distribution by hour of the day.

4.9.3 Scatter and Correlation Plots: Visualisation and Insights

Scatter plots and correlation plots were also employed to visualise and compare the features in the dataset to explore relationships and insights. Figure 4-10 shows scatterplots of attendance

against grades across all year groups. The correlation coefficient “r” across all groups ranged from 0.64 and 0.84.

Figure 4-10 Scatterplot of attendance against final grade across groups.

Correlation maps were also used to evaluate the relationships between the selected features, as shown in Figure 4-11. The correlations are shown in fractions up to 1. Strong positive correlation coefficients (>0.5) can be observed between interactions and all other features. As well as between Math grade and other features.

Figure 4-11 Correlation heatmap of selected features for MS2.

These show that student activity scores and interaction levels are useful features in tracking student progression. These can be used in the learning analytics framework for further interventions based on patterns found so far in attendance, interactions, and time patterns.

4.10 Chapter Summary

This chapter explored insights and patterns from the chosen datasets. Analysis of features revealed the following patterns:

1. Interaction comparisons: From analysis of total interactions across the students who passed or failed, it was observed that students who passed showed higher interactions with most having between 1000 - 2000 interactions, while students that failed had between 0 and 1000 interactions. Analysis of average interactions per day also highlighted that students who passed interacted between 4-7 times each day, whereas the students who failed interacted between 0-3 times each day. Exploring the days between interactions, it was observed that students who passed had shorter intervals between 2-4 days from their course content, whereas the students who failed had mostly between 3-7 days.
2. Attendance comparisons: Analysis of attendance rates across the different groups revealed that students who passed had attendance between 50-100%, whereas the students who failed had attendance mostly below 50%. Strong positive correlations between student attendance and grades were observed with correlation coefficient value between 0.68 to 0.84 across all groups.
3. Time logs and interactions: Analysis of timelines by month, day and hour revealed peak times of activity in the learning environment. Interactions peaked beginning of October with dips around holiday periods December and January. The majority of interactions occurred between 9am – 5pm each day with interactions peaking at 12pm. These insights can be useful for targeted interventions.

4. The correlation plot of features revealed that the features of attendance, quiz total, journal, workshop activity and interactions correlated positively with eventual grade.

The next chapter delves deeper into the analytics phase and explores the predictive aspect of the learning analytics framework.

Chapter 5 MACHINE LEARNING ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter focuses on the methodology and results from the application of machine learning to the data which have been extracted, processed, cleaned, and analysed with insights from the data phase. This phase focuses on the analytics phase of the learning analytics framework. It begins by explaining the analytics phase, a statistical basis for feature selection, choice of model, and results from the entire process.

5.2 Analytics

Analytical techniques were applied to extract valuable insights from the processed data. In this phase, descriptive statistics, and exploratory data analysis (EDA) techniques were employed to understand the data and obtain insights. These were covered in the previous chapter. The analytics phase also covered the feature selection and predictive model experimentation which this chapter focuses on. Figure 5-1 shows a summary of processes that make up the analytics phase which are the data analysis, data visualisation (discussed in previous chapters) and predictive models.

Figure 5-1 Summary of data analytics process.

5.3 Statistical Basis for Feature Selection

Data from 2020/2021 MC1 and MS1 (computing and science groups 1) were used to determine the statistical basis upon which the features in the dataset were chosen for analysis. Since the overall result from that year at the time was available, all features related to student activity aside from the final grade feature were evaluated to determine their usefulness as predictors for the machine learning models.

A statistical evaluation score, known as the Mutual Information score, was used for this purpose. The Mutual Information score also known as the MI score is a statistical technique that measures how useful a feature is for building predictive models. It is a measure of the mutual dependence between two random features and is calculated as the difference between the entropy of one feature and the conditional entropy of the other, given the first feature. It is considered to be a very powerful feature selection method and has inspired many studies on its estimation (Liu & Motani, 2022).

The mathematical basis of the MI Score based on (Doquire & Verleysen, 2013) is described as follows:

$$MI(X; Y) = \sum_x \sum_y p(x, y) \log \left(\frac{p(x, y)}{p(x) \cdot p(y)} \right)$$

Where:

- $MI(X; Y)$ is the Mutual Information between variables X and Y
- $p(x, y)$ is the joint probability of X and Y, which is the probability that X takes on the value x and Y takes on the value y simultaneously.
- $p(x)$ is the probability of X taking on the value of x.
- $p(y)$ is the probability of Y taking on the value y.

The MI score is equal to zero if and only if two random variables are independent and higher values indicate higher dependency. The MI score was evaluated on the MC1 and MS1 datasets, with scores for the MC1 dataset shown in table 5-1 below, these scores were evaluated against the Pass/Fail feature encoded as numbers 1 and 0 for Pass and fail respectively:

Table 5-1 MI scores for MC1 Dataset

Feature	MI Score
Grade	0.52
Quiz Total (Real)	0.36
Quiz: Quiz 6	0.35
Journal 6	0.34
Total score (Real)	0.34
Quiz Score	0.32
Attendance: Journal	0.32
Quiz: Quiz 4:	0.31
Quiz: J.6: Accuracy Check (Real)	0.31
Journal Total (Real)	0.30
Workshop:	0.30
Exams total (Real)	0.29
Workshop: J6	0.28
Workshop: J7.	0.28
Quiz: Exam 3	0.28
Journal 5	0.27
Journal 4	0.27
Workshop	0.27
Attendance: Lecture	0.26
Total Interactions	0.26
Average interactions Per Day	0.26
Journal 8	0.26
Journal 3	0.26
Workshop: J3.	0.25

Feature	MI Score
Checklist:	0.25
Quiz: Quiz 5 (a)	0.25
Average Grade	0.24
Journal Mark	0.23
Journal 7	0.23
Journal 9	0.23
Quiz: Exam 1	0.23
Quiz: Exam 2	0.22
Quiz: J3	0.22
Quiz: J8	0.21
Quiz: Quiz 3:	0.21
Quiz: Quiz 9	0.21
Quiz: Quiz 5 (b)	0.20
Workshop: J4.	0.20
Average Days Between interactions	0.18
Quiz: J4.	0.17
Quiz: Quiz 6	0.17
Quiz: Quiz 7	0.17
Quiz: J9:	0.17
Quiz: Final	0.17
Workshop: J9	0.16
Workshop: J2.	0.16
Quiz: Accuracy Check J7	0.15
Quiz: Quiz 8	0.15
Workshop: J1	0.14
Quiz: Quiz 2:	0.13
Journal 2	0.11
Quiz: Quiz 1:	0.10
Quiz: J2	0.08
Average interactions per session	0.07

A threshold of 0.1 MI Score value was chosen based on the consideration that values equal to 0 or nearest to it were almost independent of the pass/fail feature.

5.4 Machine Learning Model Development and Approach

Once relevant features were identified and filtered based on their respective MI Scores, the next phase evaluated machine learning models. To determine the predictive model, data from the 2020/2021 session were analysed, comprising 205 science students in MS1 and 106 computing students MC1. The results of the analysis informed the machine learning model selection which was subsequently validated on the 2021/2022 data, consisting of 241 math students and 132 science students. The 2021/2022 dataset was used to develop an automated feedback system for students. The 2022/2023 dataset, which included data for 214 math students and 122 science students, was employed to analyse student feedback to better understand student motivations and enhance student support services. Figure 5-2 shows the steps involved in the machine learning model development adapted from Deepak (2023).

The steps are as follows:

1. Transfer data from the data sources to a data lake.
2. Process and clean the data, which includes ensuring it is in the correct format, and removing missing values.
3. The feature engineering stage explores all features in the dataset and selects the top and most useful to build predictive models.
4. Machine learning models were trained, validated, and tested.
5. After development, the model must be continuously monitored and reevaluated as new data is acquired to ensure that it retains the necessary performance levels and adheres to predefined accuracy and fairness standards.
6. The Serve and Consume stages are where the model is made available for use in predictions. Serve refers to deploying a trained machine-learning model to make

predictions on new datasets. Consume refers to the act of using the served model to make predictions.

Figure 5-2 Machine learning model development process.

Predictive models using unsupervised learning were used to forecast student outcomes. The model was not provided with a target feature or any explicit guidance on what should be predicted. Instead, it analysed the dataset and identified inherent patterns and structures. Unsupervised learning techniques, such as clustering algorithms, create clusters or groups

based on the similarities between data points. By recognising patterns within the data without predefined labels or expectations, unsupervised learning allows the discovery of unique and previously unknown insights. The choice of evaluating unsupervised machine learning models was driven by the desire to allow the model to autonomously identify groupings within the data and the gaps in existing literature.

A review of recent advances in predictive learning analytics from 2012 to 2022 revealed that the top and most explored models in the field of learning analytics were supervised learning techniques (Sghir et al., 2023). This highlighted the need for increased evaluation of unsupervised techniques, such as clustering. (Dridi, 2021).

K-means clustering was the chosen model for this study after evaluation with two other models. The mathematics of the k-means model are below. K-means is an iterative algorithm that partitions a dataset into group of clusters denoted as “k”. The goal is to minimise the cluster variance within the identified cluster groups, which refers to the sum of the squared distances between data points and centroids for each cluster. A centroid is the geometric centre of a cluster which represents the mean location of all the data points within that cluster.

Mathematically, this is denoted as:

- k is the number of clusters.
- where n denotes the number of data points.
- x_i refers to the i th data point.
- c_j is the centroid of cluster j .

The goal is to minimise the objective function denoted as J which is the minimum sum of the squared Euclidean distances between data points and their corresponding cluster centroids.

$$J = \sum_{i=1}^n \min_j |x_i - c_j|^2$$

$|x_i - c_j|^2$ represents the Euclidean distance between a given data point x_i and c_j which is the centroid of a given cluster j .

The clustering algorithm randomly assigns and initialises a specified number of clusters “k” based on input, then assigns each data point from the dataset to the nearest centroid of each of the clusters. It continues this assignment process and updates the position of the initial clusters until it reaches a point of convergence at which J does not improve with any further update of the centroid position.

The clustering models were trained on the features in each dataset that met the MI score threshold. Subsequently, models were evaluated over different cluster numbers using silhouette scores which were used to calculate the goodness of fit of the clustering model (Shutaywi & Kachouie, 2021). Its values ranged from -1 to 1, with a value of 1 indicating a perfect clustering model and -1 representing a poor model.

Mathematically, the silhouette score is calculated as follows:

$$s(i) = \frac{b(i) - a(i)}{\max(a(i), b(i))}$$

Where:

- $s(i)$ represents the Silhouette Score for data point i
- $a(i)$: The average distance of data point i to all other data points within the same cluster representing the cohesion within the cluster.

- $b(i)$: The average distance of data point i to all data points in a different cluster, where i does not belong representing separation from other data points.

The k-means model was selected based on its superior silhouette scores compared to other unsupervised models and was utilized to generate cluster predictions on MC1 and MS1 for prediction evaluation.

Although the k-means model is an unsupervised learning technique with no labels assigned to a response feature, it can be evaluated using known labels which were excluded when training (process of teaching a computer to make predictions on given data) the model in a process known as cluster validation. This was done to evaluate the effectiveness of k-means in identifying groups of students in its predicted clusters and was treated as a supervised classification problem. This technique of “cluster validation” has been successfully used in other works (Aziz et al., 2021).

The actual labels which in this case were the “Pass/Fail” feature created in the data phase were now treated as the ground truth and compared against the predicted clusters from the k-means model. The following evaluation metrics were used: recall, precision, and overall accuracy.

The metrics were calculated using the model classifications of true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), False Positives (FP), and False Negatives (FN).

The task of assessing the ability of a model to classify whether a patient has a disease is used to explain each classification type.

A **True Positive (TP)** indicates that the predictive model predicted the patient as sick, and that the patient was sick. In this case, the illness was classified as positive. Therefore, true positives are positive predictions that are correctly classified as positive.

A **True Negative (TN)** represents a correct negative prediction. If a patient is not sick (negative), and the model predicts this correctly, it is a true negative. The negative prediction was true.

A **False Positive (FP)** represents a prediction of a positive case (sick), which is false. Therefore, if someone were not sick but predicted to be sick (positive), this would be a false positive.

Finally, a **False Negative (FN)** represents a prediction of a negative case (not sick), which is false. Therefore, if someone is sick and the model predicts that the person is healthy, this prediction is false, resulting in a false negative prediction.

Metrics derived from the classification types are as follows:

Recall:

Recall is a performance metric that evaluates a model's ability to correctly identify all relevant instances of a given class in an output category. In the context of detecting disease, recall measures the accuracy of a model in identifying all actual sick patients in a given dataset.

Recall does not consider false positives, as its primary objective is to correctly identify all sick patients. This prioritisation comes from the notion that accurately diagnosing as many sick patients as possible is crucial, even if it erroneously leads to some false positives where healthy patients are classified as sick. Recall is better metric in such prioritisation as the risk of missing a truly sick patient is far greater than that of misclassifying a healthy patient as sick.

This metric is particularly important when the goal is not to miss any actual instance of the case. Recall was the main objective of this research project. It was more important to identify as many students needing support as possible. The risk of missing any students outweighed offering more support to a few misclassified students who may not have needed it.

The formula for recall is as follows:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} = \frac{TP}{All\ actual\ Positive}$$

Precision:

Precision evaluates a classification model's positive predictions. It evaluates the correctness of all the cases predicted as positive by the model. This metric is mostly concerned with the correctness of cases predicted positive and does not prioritise if all positive cases are identified as in recall.

In the context of disease detection, it measures the accuracy of correctly classified sick patients compared with the overall number of patients classified as sick. If there is a higher risk of misclassifying patients as sick which leads to unnecessary treatment or procedures, then precision is a more relevant metric.

If a model predicts a patient as positive for a disease that would require surgery, the model is expected to be as precise as possible in classifying cases as positive. While it is undoubtedly important to identify all truly sick patients, the risk of falsely classifying a healthy patient as sick and subjecting them to unnecessary treatment, anxiety or surgery is significantly higher than the risk of missing a sick patient. Therefore, prioritising precision ensures that the model

is used responsibly and minimizes the potential for harm to patients especially the cost implications.

The formula for the precision is as follows:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} = \frac{TP}{All\ predicted\ Positive}$$

Overall Accuracy:

This evaluates the overall correctness of a classification model in identifying correct classes as compared to actual cases, so it considers all true predictions (positives and negatives) and compares it with the overall predictions. It measures how well a model predicts the different classes for a given dataset. If greater priority is not given to a predicted class, the accuracy is a better metric. So based on the disease detection context, if there was no emphasis on either predicted class or no real danger misclassifying for any particular class, accuracy would be a preferred metric.

The formula for calculating the accuracy is as follows:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} = \frac{Overall\ correct\ predictions}{All\ Predictions}$$

The results from these metrics evaluated on the 2020/2021 and 2021/2022 datasets influenced the choice of three clusters as the best for the predictive model.

5.6 Machine Learning Model Results

Clustering models were evaluated to identify different student groups in the data. The clustering models evaluated were k-means, agglomerative clustering and spectral clustering. The effectiveness of these models in identifying clusters was evaluated using silhouette scores. The results of this implementation are shown in Figure 5-3. The unsupervised learning models were evaluated across cluster values, k, from 2 and 10 for both the MC1 and MS1 datasets at week 12 (semester end).

Figure 5-3 Silhouette score graphs across all models tested.

From Figure 5-3, the k-means model performs best in 9 out of 10 tests, followed by the Agglomerative clustering model which was better in 1 case for both MC1 and MS1.

5.7 Results on Optimum Number of Student Clusters

Based on the choice of k-means, there was a need to determine the optimum choice for the number of clusters or student groups to be identified by the clustering model. An Elbow Plot was first used to investigate the computing cluster numbers using values from 1 to 10. Using this method, the point at which the rate of decrease for the sum of the squared distances changes significantly is selected as the elbow. The sum of the squared distances against the number of clusters is computed. Figure 5-4 was obtained using the elbow method. From Figure 5-4, the

choice of elbow point was unclear for cluster values 2 and 3. Therefore, additional tests were conducted to determine the suitability of each cluster.

Figure 5-4 Elbow method used to determine optimum number of clusters.

The elbow visualiser (a tool used to find the optimal number of clusters in a dataset when evaluating clustering algorithms) was applied using a distortion score and silhouette score. The distortion score calculates the sum of squared distances between each data point and its closest centroid within a cluster, while the silhouette score evaluates how similar a data point is to its own cluster compared to other clusters.

These scores are the metrics used by the visualiser. Applying these metrics gave rise to the results shown in Figure 5-5.

According to the “distortion score” metric, 3 clusters was the optimal number of clusters for the k-means model to identify useful groups. This was explored using the technique of computing silhouette scores for different cluster numbers from 2 to 10. The silhouette scores below showed that value 2 gave the highest score of 0.524.

Figure 5-5 Distortion and silhouette metric scores for MC1 and MS.

Because $k=3$ is the optimum value according to the distortion method and $k=2$ is shown as ideal using the silhouette score metric, both values were used for cluster predictions, and groups were compared against the actual final performance.

5.8 Results from Predictive Models to Identify Student Groups.

The chosen model k-means and chosen cluster numbers for evaluation were implemented on the 2020/2021 datasets MC1 (computing students) and MS1 (science) students. This implementation was to gauge the effectiveness of the model in identifying students who were not successful in the course, either by failing the course or dropping out beforehand. To determine this, cluster groups identified by k-means using both 2 clusters and 3 clusters were compared to the actual performance of the students during training. The model was also

evaluated for week 5 and week 12 dataset for MC2 and MS2. Finally, it was evaluated for week 7 and week 12 data for MC3 and MS3.

Predictions from the 2-cluster group were compared with final student pass/fail category. The 2-cluster k-means identified two groups that closely matched with the pass/fail group, whereas the 3-cluster k-means identified 3 groups; one closely matching the pass group, one group that was either way, and one group closely matching the fail group. Additional observations of the group which could go either way, showed average math grade values indicating that this group was likely to either pass or fail the course.

To calculate these metrics for the 3-cluster k-means, the likely at risk and at-risk clusters were combined for evaluation against the actual pass/fail feature which is ground truth. The following predictions for true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives for 3 clusters across all datasets are given in Table 5-2:

Table 5-2 K-means predictions using 3 clusters.

Dataset/Period	True Positive (TP)	True Negative (TN)	False Positive (FP)	False Negative (FN)
MC1	23	70	12	1
MS1	61	118	23	0
MC2(Week 5)	40	64	27	1
MC2(Week 12)	41	69	22	0
MS2(Week 5)	95	110	33	6
MS2(Week 12)	95	116	27	3
MC3(Week 7)	34	26	60	2
MC3(Week 12)	36	59	27	0
MS3(Week 7)	41	118	38	17
MS3(Week 12)	58	122	34	0

Table 5-3 shows values for TP, TN, FP, and FN for MC1, MS1, MC2 and MS2 for weeks 5 and 12 using cluster value of 2. K-means predictions for 2-clusters for MS3 and MC3 were not computed as the previous datasets showed cluster value of 3 was better at recall.

Table 5-3 K-means predictions using 2 clusters.

Dataset/Period	True Positive (TP)	True Negative (TN)	False Positive (FP)	False Negative (FN)
MC1	18	81	1	6
MS1	60	129	12	1
MC2(Week 5)	30	88	3	11
MC2(Week 12)	39	89	2	2
MS2(Week 5)	80	134	9	18
MS2(Week 12)	83	134	9	15

Figure 5-6 visualises the three clusters identified by k-means across three axes related to grade (course), Journal and Quiz totals for different MC1 and MS1, MC2, MS2, MC3, and MS3. In the clusters shown, blue represents the group (not at risk) most likely to progress through the course, the green cluster represents the group (likely at risk) which could go either way as regards the curriculum with indicators around average level. The red cluster group (at risk) are those most likely to not progress through the course based on indicators.

3D Scatter Plot with 3 Clusters MC1

3D Scatter Plot with 3 Clusters MS1

3D Scatter Plot with 3 Clusters MC2

3D Scatter Plot with 3 Clusters MS2

3D Scatter Plot with 3 Clusters MC3

3D Scatter Plot with 3 Clusters MS3

Figure 5-6 Cluster patterns found across datasets using three clusters.

Figure 5-7 presents a 3d visualisation of clusters identified by the model using two cluster values. Blue representing “likely to progress” and green representing “unlikely to progress.”

Figure 5-7 Cluster patterns found across datasets using two clusters.

From the analysis of cluster predictions and comparisons shown in the following tables with cluster results, those formed at the end of the semester were more accurate in identifying students who were at risk of failing the course than those formed early on implying that with more data coming through over the weeks of the semester, the model gets better.

The results from Table 5-4 validated on the MS2 and MC2 datasets showed that a cluster value of 3 was better at identifying more students who were at risk of not being successful with the course as early as week 5. The same process of cluster analysis for MS1 and MC1 applied to MS2 and MC2 datasets for validation, showed that 3 clusters were better at identifying students who were at risk of not passing the course as early as week 5. This was also applied to MS3 and MC3 with 3 clusters still better.

A table showing the results of Recall, Precision and Accuracy scores when the predicted clusters were compared with the actual student categories from k-means cluster validations for MS1 and MC1 is presented in Table 5-4:

Table 5-4 Cluster validation evaluation results for MS1, MC1 for 2 and 3 clusters.

Dataset (Week 12)	Recall %	Precision %	Accuracy %	Number of Clusters
Science 20/21 MS1	98.36%	83.33%	93.56%	2
Science 20/21 MS1	100%	72.62%	88.61%	3
Computing 20/21 MC1	75.00%	94.74%	93.40%	2
Computing 20/21 MC1	95.83%	65.71%	87.74%	3

5.9 Exploring Evaluation Metrics for K-means.

Based on the results in Table 5-4 from the 2020/2021 datasets, it is evident that the precision and overall accuracy decrease when the number of clusters is increased from two to three, but the recall increases for both science and computing datasets. Because of the greater importance of identifying at-risk students, a cluster value of 3 is preferable.

This choice of cluster number and model is validated on the 2021/2022 datasets (MS2 and MC2), and data were extracted at two separate times, at the fifth week when new students were mostly settled and familiar with their learning environment, and data were also collected at the end of the semester (Week 12). The k-means model, using two and three clusters, was implemented for data extracted at week 5 and the final week before exams. Predictions were made for the datasets, and when the overall results of the students were obtained, these predictions were compared with the actual results of the students. Table 5-5 shows the results from the MC2 and MS2 datasets captured at week 5 for two and three clusters.

Table 5-5 Week 5 model prediction evaluated across different metrics.

Dataset (Week 5)	Recall	Precision	Accuracy	Number of Clusters
Computing 21/22 (MC2)	73.17%	90.91%	89.39%	2
Computing 21/22 (MC2)	97.56%	59.70%	78.79%	3
Science 21/22 (MS2)	81.63%	89.89%	88.80%	2
Science 21/22 (MS2)	93.88%	73.60%	83.82%	3

As seen from Table 5-5, the pattern of an improvement in recall with an increase from two to three clusters is consistent with previous patterns while precision and accuracy drop for both groups.

Table 5-6 shows metric results obtained for MC2 and MS2 when week 12 predictions were compared with final student outcome of pass/fail:

Table 5-6 Model evaluation for MC2 & MS2 at term end

Dataset (week 12)	Recall	Precision	Accuracy	Number of Clusters
Computing 21/22 (MC2)	95.12%	95.12%	96.97%	2
Computing 21/22 (MC2)	100.00%	65.08%	83.33%	3
Science 21/22 (MS2)	84.69%	90.22%	90.04%	2
Science 21/22 (MS2)	96.94%	77.87%	87.56%	3

The results show better recall values using the 3 clusters approach for predictions made using k-means at week 5 and the end of the semester. The results also show that the performance metrics improve across recall, precision, and accuracy when predictions are made using datasets at the end of the semester. A final model evaluation test was also carried out on MS2 and MC2 using only a cluster value of 3 and time periods at week 7 and week 12. Following

this approach, the results shown in Table 5-7 were obtained. Minimum recall percentage of 70.69% was achieved in week 7.

Table 5-7 Model evaluation on MC3 and MS3 for 3 clusters at week 7

Dataset	Recall	Precision	Accuracy	Number of Clusters
Week 7 (MS3)	70.69%	51.90%	74.30%	3
Week 12 (MS3)	100.00%	63.04%	84.11%	3
Week 7 (MC3)	94.44%	36.17%	49.18%	3
Week 12 (MC3)	100.00%	57.14%	77.87%	3

At week 12, the comparison between predicted results and actual student performance using the ground truth and evaluation metrics, reaffirms that a cluster value of 3 provides a better recall at the compromise of accuracy and precision. The average accuracy across MC2, MS2, MC3 and MS3 early on (week 5 & week 7) Considering the early accuracy predictions for MC2, MC3, MS2 and MS3 was 71.52% with an average recall of 89.14%. The resulting clusters from the k-means algorithm were categorized into three groups: "at risk," "likely at risk," and "not at risk,". A combination of the "at risk" and "likely at risk" clusters named based on inspection of final course performances, was better at identifying all cases of students at risk early on.

Confusion Matrices were used to visualise the cluster validations based on True Positives, True Negatives, False Positives and False Negative values which are easily seen via the heatmap, as shown in the MC3 and MS3 visuals in Figure 5-8:

Figure 5-8 Heatmap showing confusion matrices for MC3 and MS3.

Figure 5-8 shows comparison of predicted cluster categories with actual outcomes. The number of students in each box correspond to the True Positives, True Negatives, False Positives and False Negative predictions from the model upon which the metrics were calculated for MC3 and MS3.

5.10 Chapter Summary

This chapter explored the analytics phase of the learning analytics cycle using unsupervised machine learning techniques. Feature selection technique using MI score highlighted features on quiz, journal, attendance, workshop, interactions and average days between interactions as the most useful for exploring the predictive models. The k-means, agglomerative and spectral machine learning techniques were explored with k-means outperforming the others based on silhouette score analysis. Initial analysis of the k-means model highlighted that cluster values of 2 (based on distortion score) or 3 (based on silhouette score) were best for analysis. Building predictive models based on those values highlighted that 3 clusters were better for identifying student groups at risk of non-progression than the 2-cluster predictions. Based on recall, the k-means model scored an average of 89.14% based on early predictions (week 5 and week 7) with minimum recall of 70.69%. The overall accuracy of the model was 71.52%. The accuracy of the k-means model, using non personally identifying data, highlight the potential of unsupervised learning in identifying student groups and for model development. The benefit of early detection students that need help, based on learning analytics, can support educational institutions with timely information to make informed decisions.

The next chapter explored the value of using automated and personalised student feedback as a form of intervention in the action phase of the learning analytics framework. Off-the-shelf solutions, such as inbuilt Moodle analytics, were not used because they were closed source, meaning it would be difficult to design, customize, and understand how they work. The open-source tools, like Jupyter Notebooks used in this approach, made the design and experimentation with ML models and analytics very easy.

Chapter 6 STUDENT FEEDBACK, INTERVENTIONS AND RESULTS

6.1 Introduction

This chapter focuses on the methodology and results of using student dashboards and personalised student feedback as interventions to address the action phase of the learning analytics framework. It also discusses the methods for collecting student data and their perceptions of the personalised feedback forms. This is a key component of the action phase of the learning analytics framework which involves taking action based on insights from the data and analytics phases.

6.2 Dashboard Development Using Power BI.

Developing a dashboard, which can be shared with stakeholders and educators, was one intervention taken in this phase, so that information can easily be understood and shared with relevant stakeholders. Power BI is a software created by Microsoft, which was used for this purpose. It allowed users to visualise and analyse data from various sources through interactive interfaces. The Power BI software proved to be an invaluable tool in the development of a comprehensive dashboard that effectively visualised the machine learning clusters identified by the model, as well as the interaction patterns and specific course components with which students engaged. This was achieved through extracting the output data frame with predicted groups from the k-means and connecting it as data source to the Power BI interface. The dashboard also provided insights into the number of students within each category, displaying their names to facilitate personalised analysis.

Creating the dashboard involved several intricate processes, including dashboard design, establishing table connections and relationships, and constructing charts specifically tailored for this purpose.

The dashboard design phase involved careful consideration of the layout, colour schemes, and visual elements to ensure optimal data representation and user experience. Each component of the dashboard was strategically positioned to convey information intuitively and facilitate quick comprehension of the insights derived from the machine learning clusters. The dashboard was designed to be a powerful tool for educators and stakeholders to navigate and interpret complex data effortlessly.

Table connections and relationships are crucial for effectively integrating and organising data within the dashboard. Various data tables, such as machine learning cluster results, student interactions, and course components were interconnected to provide a cohesive view of the relationships and dependencies between different features. These connections required meticulous data modelling and utilisation of Power BI's robust features for managing complex data relationships.

Chart buildings also played a pivotal role in the creation of dashboards. Several types of charts were employed to represent machine learning clusters, interaction patterns, and course components. Each chart was carefully selected to present the data in the most informative and visually appealing manner. The selection of appropriate chart types, such as scatter plots, bar graphs, or line charts, was determined by the nature of the data being visualised and insights sought. By leveraging the diverse range of chart options available in Power BI, the dashboard

effectively enhanced communication ease with stakeholders and clarity regarding student progression.

The Power BI dashboard was designed to facilitate data-driven discussions, collaboration, and the enhancement of educational outcomes. The following steps were taken to design the dashboard based on the data and model predictions:

1. The Power BI desktop application was installed on the server where the data and the developed model were stored.
2. Once the Application was installed, administrator logins were completed and the “Get Data” option on Power BI desktop page is used to connect to data .
3. Data are loaded from this data store with specific tables relevant to the created dashboard.
4. Table relationships were defined to ensure efficiency, within this study, log files’ “User full name” feature is connected to course activity “full name” feature establishing a relationship between the tables for aggregation.
5. Data visualisations were created on the canvas using the drag and drop interface of Power BI onto the report canvas. These visualisations are customised, resized, or modified using the control options available.
6. Slicers and filters in Power BI were added and allowed users to interact with the dashboard dynamically. It was useful for viewing subsets of data after the table relationships were defined.
7. Sharing and collaboration were performed using the share and publish options in the Power BI interface.

A sample dashboard created using the steps described above is shown in Figure 6-1. This dashboard provides a comprehensive view of the cluster analysis results, enabling educators and administrators to easily interpret and utilise the information.

Figure 6-1 Power BI dashboard developed to support intervention.

Power BI was used as a dashboarding and visualisation tool because of its intuitive and visually appealing user interface. It also supports a wide range of data integration sources which offer scalability to the dashboard and makes it easy to share the dashboard and visualisation by leveraging the existing IT infrastructure at the university. It also easily integrates with other services within the Microsoft ecosystem, which supports student account registration and identity management. Power BI offers real-time monitoring and facilitates collaboration at scale.

6.3 Personalised Automated Feedback

Providing personalised feedback was identified as a crucial intervention in the learning analytics framework to ensure that the insights obtained are used effectively. The results were shared with students, educators, and other stakeholders. Personalised feedback was provided to the student groups, based on the analysis results. The exploration of automated feedback in this project involved a synergistic combination of Power Automate, Jupyter Notebook, and API access to enhance the feedback delivery process. By leveraging these technologies, students were provided timely and personalised feedback and valuable insights were gathered through a student survey form. Power Automate played a pivotal role in orchestrating the automated feedback process. In addition, it provides a user-friendly interface to expedite the feedback delivery.

Jupyter Notebook, serving as the primary development environment, played a crucial role in the automation of feedback generation. The Python code was developed within the Jupyter Notebook to process and analyse the relevant data, enabling the generation of personalised feedback based on predetermined criteria and rules. This ensured that the feedback provided to the students was tailored to their specific needs and circumstances.

API access further enriched the automated feedback process by enabling the seamless integration of external systems. APIs serve as bridges between different platforms, facilitating data retrieval and exchange. By leveraging API access, the project can tap into external data sources and incorporate additional insights into the feedback generation process, enriching the feedback content and enhancing its relevance.

Feedback was provided to the sample student groups, allowing them to benefit from timely and individualised guidance. Additionally, the project team sought feedback from the students themselves through a survey feedback form. This form, integrated into the automated feedback delivery process, served as a means for students to express their thoughts, opinions, and suggestions regarding the intervention and areas of improvement.

6.4 Design of Feedback

The design of automated feedback began by determining thresholds for what kind of feedback the students are expected to receive based on their interaction and learning information.

The determination of threshold values for these comments used in email automation relies on the educator's discretion, and the number of comment categories can be expanded if needed. For this research, comments were limited to 2-3 categories. However, the system is flexible enough to increase the number of categories to meet the personalised feedback requirements of educators. The essential aspect is to make decisions regarding the type of comments that should be assigned to students based on their scores within predefined categories established by the educator. Emails were already integrated into the Virtual Learning Environment, and students get most of their information sent there. This influenced the choice of using emails as a starting point to experiment with personalized feedback.

Thresholds were established for the Journal, Quiz, Attendance, and Interactions features. Individual comments were generated for each student based on the scores within each feature. Considering the journal score as an example, if a student achieved a score of 4.5 or higher, they performed well, and the corresponding comment "Your total journal score was above average. Way to go! Keep it up" is assigned. If the first condition is not met, the code proceeds to the

next condition, checking if the student's score is 2.5 or higher. In this case, the comment "Your total journal score was above average, good one, keep trying..." was assigned. Lastly, for scores below 2.5, the student is given the comment "Your Total Journal performance was below average. We know that math can be challenging, but we believe that with consistent and frequent work, you can achieve better outcomes."

The automation process applies the same logic to the Quiz, Attendance, and Interactions features, with thresholds and corresponding comments set by the educator.

After generating new features with comments, a preview of the data was conducted to verify that the features were created correctly, and that the assigned comments were aligned with the corresponding scores, as illustrated in Figure 6-2.

Out[41]:

Lecture_attendance	attendancecomment	Quiz_score	quizcomment	Journal_attendance	Journal_score	Journal_without	journalcomment	Exam_Contribution
63.16	You need to attend your classes often to impro...	1.5	Your performance on the Quizzes was below aver...	78.57	1.21	1.54	Your Total Journal performance was below avera...	0.00
68.42	You need to attend your classes often to impro...	4.5	You performed well above average on your Quizz...	85.71	2.34	2.73	Your Total Journal performance was below avera...	6.07
94.74	Your attendance rate has been great this semes...	4.5	You performed well above average on your Quizz...	100.00	4.80	4.80	Your Total Journal score was way above the ave...	7.86
77.78	Your attendance rate has been great this semes...	4.5	You performed well above average on your Quizz...	83.33	3.03	3.64	Your Total Journal score was above average. Go...	6.79
22.22	You need to attend your classes often to impro...	0.0	Your performance on the Quizzes was below aver...	16.67	0.06	0.38	Your Total Journal performance was below avera...	0.00
...
50.00	You need to attend your classes often to impro...	0.0	Your performance on the Quizzes was below aver...	16.67	0.00	0.00	Your Total Journal performance was below avera...	0.00
100.00	Your attendance rate has been great this semes...	4.5	You performed well above average on your Quizz...	100.00	3.60	3.60	Your Total Journal score was above average. Go...	6.43
73.68	Your attendance rate has been great this	3.0	You performed above the	85.71	3.07	3.59	Your Total Journal score	7.14

Figure 6-2 Preview of combined data after automated comments generated.

A configuration was established to integrate Microsoft Power Automate with the output generated by a Python script, enabling the dispatch of emails using a pre-designed template. The data containing individual comments were directed to Power Automate, where an email template containing general information for all students was generated. The Python request package (Chandra et al., 2015) was utilised to establish the connection between the data with individual comments and the Power BI API. In the provided code snippet, the section marked "http://" should be substituted with the URL link provided by Power Automate during flow creation. This is illustrated in Figure 6-3.

```
In [51]: ▶ import requests
count=0
url='http://XXXXXXXXXXXXX'
for i in testing_stream:
    headers = {'Content-type': 'application/json', 'Accept': 'text/plain'}
    r = requests.post(url, data=json.dumps(i), headers=headers)
    print(r)
    count+=1
```

Figure 6-3 Connecting to Power Automate for email automation.

Figure 6-4 is an interface for automated feedback design where data from the API was designed to automate the email personalisation. A template was created with data content from the API. This template holds the email body for each student, but the personalised element comes from the dynamic data content which is fed through the API.

Figure 6-4 Customizing Power Automate to pick values from automation.

As shown in Figure 6-4, once data from the Python script is connected to the flow, the feature values are shown as dynamic content. Dynamic content refers to data produced from an action that acts as a placeholder for each row of data coming through the API.

With this dynamic content, once the template is created and customised, personalised comments and different values are replaced for each email sent from the template.

This was customized and emails were sent out to students within minutes after a few test emails were sent to confirm the email preview which would be received by student, Figure 6-5 below is a preview of a test emails sent.

Maths 1.1 Personalised Feedback Form

Group #

Dear *student*

We hope you are enjoying first year maths. Here is a summary of your progress in maths so far.

Journal Work (20%) (out of 5%)	Quizzes (15%) (out of 4.5%)	Exams (65%) Week 7 (out of 10%)	Marks so far (out of 19.5%)	Average Mark so far %
3.3%	1.5%	7.0%	11.8%	60.7%

Remember there is no such thing as a maths gene. All our brains have a remarkable capacity to grow and change and with **frequent practice and effort**.

Lecture Class Participation
Your participation at lectures **100.0%**
You are attending most of your lectures, good effort.

Journal Work (Mandatory Attendance)
Your participation in journals is **100.0%**
Great effort on attending all your journal classes.
Your mark for Journal 1 and 2 is averaging at **66.7%**. Because your journal mark is weighted by attendance your mark becomes **66.7%**. This effort contributes towards **3.3%** out of 5% available so far for journal work.

Moodle Quiz Effort
Of the **3 semester 1 quizzes so far**, you have achieved 100%, **mastery** in 1.0. This equates to **1.5%** of the 4.5% available for quizzes. *You have achieved a 10/10 well done on trying. Keep going until you achieve 10 on all quizzes, they are a great way of learning through retrieval and practice and build strong neural pathways.*
Only the quizzes that you get 100% in will contribute towards your final mark. When we make a mistake, synapses fire in your brain which means learning occurs. Quizzes are a great opportunity to practice and learn from your mistakes and are used again in exam questions.

Week 7 Exam
You achieved **70.0%** the week 7 exam. This contributes to **7.0%** of overall marks in maths.
Please free to ask questions in lectures or in journal classes.

Figure 6-5 Personalised sample email sent out to students as an intervention step.

After confirming the satisfactory appearance of the test emails, they were automatically sent to the respective students based on their uniquely generated comments.

6.5 App Prototype Development for Feedback

To streamline and automate the process of delivering personalised feedback to students, a prototype application was developed and tested using the PowerApps. This application, built as a canvas app, aims to efficiently integrate various data sources and facilitate the delivery of automated feedback to students. Throughout the development and testing phases, a small sample dataset was used to ensure the effectiveness and reliability of the application.

The prototype application integrated data sources from the sample dataset, enabling the app to access and utilise the necessary information to generate personalised feedback. The data sources were carefully selected and configured to align with the specific requirements of the feedback delivery. By establishing these connections, the application was able to retrieve relevant data and incorporate them into the feedback generation workflow.

6.6 Survey Design Using Microsoft Forms

A survey was created to collect students' perspectives on receiving personalised feedback and the preferred mechanism of feedback delivery. The survey was created using Microsoft Forms, the link to the created survey was embedded in the automated feedback email sent to the selected students, and the students' responses were collected and stored online.

Microsoft forms were chosen for this purpose because they integrated easily with other tools in the Microsoft office suite, which has been used in Automated Feedback. As many students

were not on campus at some time due to COVID, this was a much more convenient way to get their perspective.

6.7 Survey Results from the Student Feedback Survey

The following results were obtained across the two years of intervention for the MC2, MS2, MC3, and MS3 dataset groups to ascertain student views on the automated and personalised feedback they received. A total of 392 students from the groups responded to the survey:

- 75 students from MC2 group
- 132 students from MS2 group
- 62 students from MC3 group
- 115 students from MS3 group
- 8 students who declined to consent and did not complete the survey.

The survey included the following questions:

1. Rate the personalised feedback email you received (5=really good, 1=poor)?
2. Comment freely on your choice of rating above
3. What is your preferred method of receiving this kind of feedback?
4. How did the language of the feedback make you feel?

The following results were obtained from analysis of the responses obtained:

For survey question 1, results of the feedback form received from a section on students rating was 4.51 out of 5 which showed that 90.2% (n=354) of them found the feedback very useful. 93% (n=365) percent rated it either 4 or 5.

Results were obtained from 203 students who answered question 2 commenting freely on their choice of rating. Figure 6-6 below shows the word cloud of the most common responses. Most of the responses highlighted the perceived benefits of such feedback, a few other students believed it could be more personalised and 1% (n=2) of students found it a bit difficult to understand.

Figure 6-6 Word cloud of question 2 responses.

Figure 6-7 shows some of the comments on question 2.

There is a lot of information in the email and it s also very easy to understand.
-
Very good wayof receiving personalised feedback
It provided me with all I needed to know about how I was getting on with the course
I think i'm satisfied with my feedback.
it was a bit hard to understand what it all meant at first
its good
It was good
My personalised feedback is very useful for understanding my progress

Figure 6-7 Sample comments on question 2.

In response to survey question 3, analysis showed 82% (n=169) of students preferred to receive this kind of feedback by email, as shown by the word cloud in Figure 6-8.

respondents (82%) answered **email** for this question. ...

Figure 6-8 Word cloud showing student preferences in receiving personalized feedback.

In response to the final question on how the language used for this feedback made students feel, there were 95% (n=196) positive responses with students using various words like good, encouraging, motivating, professional, happy, and other positive adjectives to describe their interpretation of the language used in the feedback forms. Some of these responses are shown in the word cloud generated from the responses in Figure 6-9.

Figure 6-9 Word cloud showing how language used made students feel.

6.8 Chapter Summary

Chapter 6 explored the approaches followed in developing a learning analytics dashboard and an automated feedback system personalised to the students. The design of the feedback system involved setting course thresholds, generating individual comments based on each student's score and integrating with Power Automate for email automation. The overwhelmingly high ratings from this feedback system highlights its usefulness as an intervention step in supporting students through learning analytics.

Chapter 7 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

7.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the overall conclusions, guided by answers to the research questions and objectives of the study. The research questions were:

- Can historical data (three years) uncover patterns and insights between successful and unsuccessful students based on their interactions and learning behaviour?
- Can machine learning models predict at risk/struggling students with good accuracy?
What are the early indicators that predict students' success or disengagement?
- How effective is automated and personalised feedback as an intervention method?

The study objectives were as follows:

Table 7-1 Research Objectives

Objective 1:	Create a data pipeline and visualisation system for data ingestion and analysis
Objective 2:	Explore the application of Machine Learning (ML) technologies for learning analytics in Higher Education.
Objective 3:	Identify meaningful predictors for student success, using both real-time and historical data.
Objective 4:	Validate ML models and explore impact of personalised feedback
Objective 5:	Extend the body of knowledge of applied machine learning in Irish and International Higher Education settings.

7.2 Research Question Answers

Can historical data (three years) uncover patterns and insights between successful and unsuccessful students based on their interactions and learning behaviour?

Historical data analysis effectively uncovered distinct behavioural patterns between successful and unsuccessful students, which lead to a better understanding of student behaviour. There were also key indicators of student success found from data analysis. Analysis of features showed that higher interaction frequency, shorter gaps between interactions, and better attendance consistently correlated with better academic performance. Potential times for targeted interventions were also uncovered from patterns in student engagement. This information can be used to improve decision making on the timing of targeted interventions. Monitoring these indicators on an ongoing basis would be a valuable tool for identifying struggling students early leading to more proactive retention strategy and learner support from the institution.

Can machine learning models predict risk/struggling students with good accuracy? What are the early indicators that predict students' success or disengagement?

Unsupervised machine learning models evaluated, demonstrated promising results in predicting students' success and risk of disengagement. The results indicated that the models, particularly the k-means clustering algorithm, showcased significant potential in identifying at-risk students early in the academic term.

The evaluation metrics which included recall, precision and accuracy based on ground truth indicated the effectiveness of the model. Experimenting with cluster values of 2 and 3 showed reliable identification of at-risk students with early recall accuracy exceeding 70%.

Feature selection, using the Mutual Information (MI) score, assisted in pinpointing relevant features significantly associated with student outcomes. Features such as quiz scores, attendance, journal activity, and interaction frequency emerged as critical indicators of student success.

Analysis of model predictions on early data taken at week 5 and week 7, revealed that the model can predict student outcomes accurately and comparing this with model predictions made towards the end of semester showed that the model accuracy improves over time. The ability of models to accurately identify at least 70% of students at risk of non-progression as early as week 5 shows the value in leveraging this approach to support student learning.

These findings highlight the usefulness of machine learning models for proactive student support and intervention based on the early indicators. Information from these can assist educational institutions to best cater for individual student needs.

How effective is automated and personalised feedback as an intervention method?

This research demonstrated the efficacy of automated and personalised feedback as an intervention method. The overwhelming positive perception from students on receiving this form of feedback and their preference for receiving it via email highlights the need for building such systems at scale. 93% of students (n=365) found the feedback style very useful with comments from student showing great positive perception. This highlights automated and personalized feedback as an invaluable intervention tool in educational settings which fosters positive learning experiences and engagement.

7.3 Research Objectives and Achievements

Objective 1: Create a data pipeline and visualisation system for data ingestion and analysis.

A robust data pipeline which incorporates various stages of data collection, cleaning, analysis, model development and integration was created for the purposes of this research. It was designed to incorporate data from diverse sources within higher education ensuring that data for learning analytics is in a form that is suitable for analysis. This pipeline fostered the data processing and model development for this research. The pipeline also incorporates ease of API usage which ensures seamless data extraction and incorporation to a database.

A visualisation system using Power BI was also developed as a prototype to show a comprehensive dashboard through interactive visualisations in the form of charts and graphs. This allows stakeholders in education to interpret data easily. This visualisation system easily integrates with the data pipeline and other data sources. This ensures clear, concise and meaningful data interpretation for education environments. Based on this research, it is clear that the implementation of a data pipeline and visualisation system such as have been investigated has significant potential value for improving student outcomes and experiences in third level institutions. These systems should be a priority activity for higher education institutions to ensure that student needs are proactively met.

Objective 2: Explore the application of Machine Learning technologies for learning analytics in Higher Education

Machine learning models (unsupervised) were explored as detailed in Chapter 5. The use of these models for predictive modelling in learning analytics were also evaluated. The k-means model was the most effective compared to others which were evaluated with accuracy metrics exceeding 70%. This can be used to inform targeted interventions for at-risk students, potentially reducing the overall number of interventions required compared to a full-class approach. Notwithstanding, it is important to note that it is not possible to identify all at-risk students using this method as there are unforeseen circumstances that may arise and some students who may not be at risk may require other forms of support. This exploration showed that distinct student groups can be successfully identified based on their patterns of engagement with their courses. This exploration also provided part of the answer to the second research question.

Objective 3: Identify meaningful predictors for student success, using both real-time and historical data.

The research identified meaningful predictors for student success by analysing both real time and historical data. Factors relating to interactions, attendance, quizzes, journal activity and days between interactions were evaluated to rank their significance in finding patterns in different student groups. This enabled the identification of important indicators for student success which are useful for creating targeted educational interventions.

Achieving this objective also partly answered the second research question. Research findings emphasised the value of learning analytics in comprehending student progression, aligning with findings by Lee O'Farrell, (2017). It additionally showed that poor engagement with the learning material is an important indicator of student success reaffirming research findings by Q. Hu et al., (2021) which underscored engagement as an important indicator of success.

Objective 4: Validate ML models and explore the impact of personalized feedback.

The selected machine learning model following the exploration using MS1 and MC1 was validated iteratively on MC2, MS2, MC3 and MS3. This validation aimed to ensure their accuracy in predicting student success and identifying at-risk students. The study also examined the impact of automated and personalised feedback utilising tools and development environments such as: Power Automate, Jupyter Notebooks and API development, to facilitate the automation and personalisation of feedback delivery to students based on the identified student groups based on engagement patterns and performance metrics.

Results from evaluating unsupervised machine learning methods on non-personally identifying data showed that this technique offers high accuracies in detecting students at risk early on. Comparing this with other studies using demographic-based data such as Gray (2015), showed comparable results emphasising the value of using only data generated from the virtual learning environment for predictive models in learning analytics.

The high positive perception of the feedback received by the students further revealed its importance in enhancing learning analytics aligning with research conducted by Cavus Ezin & Yilmaz, (2022) highlighting the usefulness of feedback as an intervention step.

Some of the practical issues associated with the development and implementation of feedback which were uncovered by Biggam (2010), were addressed by the design of the automated and personalised student feedback system. This incorporated feedback based on the groupings identified by the predictive model, leading to feedback which was well perceived by students in each of these groups.

Objective 5: Extend the body of knowledge of applied machine learning in Irish and International Higher Education settings.

Research findings from this study contributed to extending the body of knowledge regarding the application of machine learning technology and automated feedback in the field of learning analytics. The exploration of data insights from historical data, predictive modelling and implementation of personalised feedback mechanisms offered valuable insights for educational practitioners, policymakers, and researchers. This has been shared with the community through conferences and research publications from this study. These findings have broader implications for improving intervention measures, creating a culture of data-driven decision making in universities, improving student retention, and creating better learning experiences for students globally.

Findings from this study also highlighted the added value gained by tracking student activities and engagement with course components. Significant value in the log files which track student activity within courses was uncovered. This echoes the research findings made of Anthony (2021) when discussing the value of tracking these activities. The research also reinforces the effectiveness of using machine learning to optimize learning analytics, aligning with research

studies conducted by Kuleto et al. (2021) and Waheed et al. (2020). Their work also highlighted the transformative power of this technology in enhancing teaching and learning practices.

Overall, the exploration of a new approach for enhancing learning analytics using machine learning techniques showed great potential making use of only data generated within the institution. This partly addresses the issues and challenges regarding the collection, storage and use of sensitive data related to students. Most of these issues relate to information confidentiality and complexities with obtaining such information and using them for learning analytics.

7.4 Areas of Future Work

1. Conducting research using datasets from other faculties within the university to explore whether the patterns identified in this study are consistent across these disciplines. Results may differ across other disciplines like arts, biology etc.
2. Investigating and comparing the performance of different models using both supervised and unsupervised approaches to explore their relevance and performance in learning analytics. This could offer a more complete understanding of which models best suit different educational contexts in learning analytics.
3. Additional investigation of log files data to explore other patterns which could lead to better identification of student groups.
4. Comparing the performance with integrating external data sources such as biographical data following data protection guidelines. To enhance the depth of the research work, external data sources may be integrated in a future study and

explore how it improves the performance of the model developed using available data within the institution.

5. The research completed highlights the potential for the development of an application to scale the process of learning analytics modelling and creation of personalised feedback which can support educators with overcoming challenges with giving and receiving feedback. A prototype was developed to streamline and automate the process of delivering personalised feedback to students using PowerApps, however more work is required to make it much more efficient and scalable.
6. Future work should explore retention strategies in partnership with students to understand their needs and motivations better. This can lead to creation of tailored interventions to support their learning which leads to improved progression rates.

7.5 Chapter Summary

The utilisation of time-series data offers a promising avenue for uncovering the temporal patterns that may influence student performance. By examining the sequential nature of interactions, it becomes possible to discern trends, behaviours, or critical periods that significantly impact academic outcomes. Such insights can inform the design and implementation of targeted interventions tailored to the specific needs of each cluster.

The findings highlight the potential of unsupervised learning methods, particularly the k-means algorithm, in predicting student performance based on Moodle VLE interactions and module activities. The identified clusters offer a valuable framework for implementing targeted

interventions aimed at improving students' engagement and academic outcomes. Future research endeavours will expand on these findings by investigating temporal patterns in student interactions to extract qualitative insights. Ultimately, these efforts will contribute to the development of more effective and personalised educational approaches that foster student success and engagement.

The results of this research show that automating personalised feedback for students holds positive potential to be of value to students and support educators to overcome the challenges of having to give this kind of feedback manually, considering the volume of students and time commitment required.

The research concludes that the adoption of a data science approach enhanced by machine learning will provide stakeholders with greater insights, enhance student engagement, improve student outcomes which will enhance student success. It is recommended that this approach to enhancing teaching and learning be widely adopted across higher education institutions as it provides the opportunity to better understand and support students who may be at risk of non-progression at their various universities.

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